

PREDICT-6G

D2.3

Release 2 of PREDICT-6G MDP innovations

PREDICT-6G

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Authors	<p>Elena Ferrari, Rafael Rosales (INT)</p> <p>Péter Szilágyi, Tamás Kárász, Szabolcs Nováczki, Zoltán Vincze, Csaba Vulkán (NOK)</p> <p>Claudio Zunino, Manuel Cheminod, Stefano Vitturi (CNR)</p> <p>Abinaya Babu, Muhammad Awais Jadoon, Sebastian Robitzsch (IDE)</p> <p>Margarita Cabrera-Bean, Youssef El Kaisi, Olga Muñoz, Josep Vidal, Javier Villares (UPC)</p> <p>Marc Mollà, Rocio Dominguez (ERC)</p> <p>Claudio Casetti, Carla Fabiana Chiasserini (POLITO)</p>
Reviewers	Antonio de la Oliva (UC3M)

Abstract

This document is the second version of the deliverable on multi-domain data plane innovations in the PREDICT-6G project. The deliverable collects and reports advances compared to the initial version (D2.1) that were produced since then. The technical topics are following the theme set by the previous version, such as improvement of deterministic mechanisms in lower layers, and handling of non-deterministic domains; additionally, this document contains original reflections to topics such as deployment domains and device side impact of PREDICT-6G. Finally, the deliverable provides a roadmap for the data plane features during the rest of the project's runtime and collects relevant publications.

Keywords

multi-domain data plane, MDP, TSN, 3GPP, Wi-Fi, DetNet, non-deterministic, devices

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*** Deliverable types:**

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Acronyms and definitions

3GPP	3GPP 3rd Generation Partnership Project
ADU	Application Data Unit
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AICP	AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control-Plane
AP	Access Point
BE	Best Effort
BER	Bit Error Rate
BLER	Block Error Rate
BS	Base Station
CL	Capacity Limited
DetNet	Deterministic Networking
DL	Downlink
DQN	Deep Q-Network
DT	Digital Twin
DUG	Data Unit Group
E2E	End-to-End
eBPF	extended Berkeley Filters
FRER	Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability
GCL	Gate Control List
GM	Grand Master

gNB	gNodeB
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
MDP	Multi-domain Data Plane
MLO	Multi-Link Operation
MPLS	Multi-Protocol Label Switching
MS	Managed Service
MTU	Maximum Transmission Unit
NIC	Network Interface Card
NN	Neural Network
OAI	OpenAirInterface
OFDMA	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access
PAREO	Packet ARQ, Replication, Elimination and Ordering
PDB	Packet Delay Budget
PREOF	Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Function
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
QL	Q-Learning
QoS	Quality of Service
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RTT	Round Trip Time

rTWT	Restricted Target Wake Time
RU	Resource Units
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SS	Static Splitter
STA	Station
TDD	Time Division Multiplexing
TDMA	Time Division Multiple Access
TLV	Type Length Values
TS	Time Sensitive
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
TWT	Target Wake Time
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
URLLC	Ultra-reliable low-latency communication
USRP	Universal Software Radio Peripheral
WP	Work Package
WTPS	Waiting Time Proportional Splitter
XDP	Express Data Paths
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

Table of partners

Short Name	Partner
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
NOK	Nokia Solutions and Networks KFT
ERC	Ericsson Espana SA
INT	Intel Deutschland GMBH
TID	Telefonica Investigacion Digital SL
ATOS	ATOS IT Solutions and Services Iberia SL
GES	Gestamp Servicios SA
NXW	Nextworks
COG	Cognitive Innovations Private Company
SIM	Software Imagination & Vision SRL
AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO Alpha Lab MTU
POLITO	Politecnico di Torino
UPC	Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
UNIPD	Universita degli Studi di Padova
IDE	InterDigital Europe Ltd

1 Executive summary

The multi-domain data plane (MDP) of PREDICT-6G provides mechanisms that enable different technologies to collaborate in creating an end-to-end deterministic service. The MDP builds on existing technologies (standards, pre-standards or new/experimental) that are at different level of maturity and bring different capabilities in terms of flow monitoring, packet scheduling, latency management, or resiliency features.

Enhancing or creating deterministic mechanisms is in the scope of WP2 and this deliverable (D2.3), which reports advances in L2 and L3 technologies achieved in the PREDICT-6G project since the first release of MDP innovations in D2.1 (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023).

This deliverable focuses on novel or further L2 and L3 developments in dynamic scheduling algorithms, latency monitoring and evaluation, TSN on Wi-Fi and 3GPP, Data Unit Groups, implementation of a DetNet router, and cross-domain TSN integration using DetNet over Wi-Fi, 3GPP and L2 TSN domains.

In terms of data plane architecture and cross-domain integration, D2.3 is first to report on PREDICT-6G's approach of the impact on terminal devices; and handling domains with non-deterministic network stack (i.e., lacking explicit deterministic features). Additionally, we report on PREDICT-6G's approach and assumptions towards multiple domains including the aspects of administrative and technical domains.

The deliverable reports the latest definition of the OpenAPIs that are exposed by PREDICT-6G's MDP and consumed by the control and management plane called AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control-Plane (AICP). Finally, the roadmap to the MDP features is presented to link the innovations to the realization plan.

Key contributions of the deliverable:

- Slice-aware resource allocation and admission control strategy in Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) access.
- Advances on using Wi-Fi 802.11be restricted target wake time mechanism to emulate TSN, already reporting learnings from simulations.
- Seamless roaming with multi-radio / multi-link operation in Wi-Fi 7.
- Distributed technology agnostic mechanism to emulate deterministic features in networks with no explicit support for determinism.
- Report on successful cross-domain integration of TSN, Wi-Fi and 3GPP using DetNet in a real testbed using commercial equipment.

2 Introduction

This document is the second release of the multi-domain data plane (MDP) innovations produced by PREDICT-6G, reporting on the advances since the first release of MDP in D2.1 in August 2023 (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023).

This deliverable is structured to maintain continuity with D2.1 in terms of most of the topics but also be efficient by reporting novelties created in the PREDICT-6G project in the last 16 months rather than reproducing content that was already published. To this end, each subsequent section starts with a summary of the updates that is reported in this D2.3 in comparison to the first MDP release in D2.1, with references guiding towards the original content whenever there is a direct mapping between previous and current work. The details of the new achievements are then reported in each section.

In addition to topics where the continuation of work since D2.1 provides a natural (incremental or substantial) progress in the reported results; additional topics are also introduced in this deliverable. These are either topics that were not yet investigated at the time of D2.1 but were already on the project's agenda, or ones that were inspired by interactions with the External Advisory Board and project reviewers during the midterm review. We are grateful for those inputs as they enrich the perspective of PREDICT-6G and starting to report them in this deliverable enables to share those contributions with all followers of the PREDICT-6G project.

The rest of this document is organized as follows. Section 3 is dedicated to new result to enhancing deterministic mechanisms in the layer 2 of various technologies, most notably Wi-Fi and 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), as well as incorporating TSN into these domains. The section starts by reporting on extensive theoretical and simulation work related to scheduling algorithms applicable to a mixture of traffic classes, which is relevant in any real-world deterministic service deployments that must serve not only deterministic but other types of traffic on the same infrastructure. Next, a flexible latency evaluation method is described that can be used with any network technology. This is followed by an extensive work on using the recent restricted Target Wake Time, part of 802.11be, to emulate determinism in Wi-Fi. Simulation results are already provided reporting on the efficiency of the mechanisms. The section also reports on how to improve the determinism of OpenAirInterface through Linux kernel-based scheduling mechanisms to become a better alternative for researching 3GPP networks. Section 4 introduces network and transport technology related novel results, first by discussing updates in the Data Unit Groups (former PDU sessions in (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023)) to coherently handle packet segmentation in large applications payloads, and then presenting an achievement to produce a Deterministic Networking (DetNet) router in software using XDP and eBPF.

Section 5 is reporting on a mixture of continued and novel topics in the area of data plane architecture and cross-domain integration. The section starts with the discussion of the impact and requirements of deterministic services on end devices, outlining PREDICT-6G's assumptions in the scope of the current project as well as potential steps. The next topic is the target deployment assumptions and multi-domain considerations, reflecting on comments from the project's internal review. Next, the section reports on results of integrating TSN to 5G and Wi-Fi using real commercial devices and DetNet as and the end-to-end layer. The section provides a comprehensive discussion of introducing deterministic capabilities into non-deterministic devices and networks.

Section 6 provides a brief update on the OpenAPIs provided by the MDP towards the AICP. The section summarizes the semantic of the time synchronization, deterministic service provisioning, exposure and measurements APIs and points to the formal specification accessible in PREDICT-6G's GitLab.

Section 7 reports on the roadmap of the innovations and results that will be showcased in either of the Open Labs (5TONIC and Nokia) until the end of the project.

The deliverable finishes with concluding remarks in Section 8 and a list of publications in Section 9.

3 Enhancements at Layer 2

3.1 Summary of updates

This section contains the last updates on the enhancement at Layer 2 produced by the Task 2.1 of the Work Package 2 (WP2). We follow the same structure proposed in (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023), where we grouped the research and innovation activities in clusters, according to their main topic.

Regarding *Dynamic Scheduling for 3GPP OFDMA*, in (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023), we presented the general architecture and preliminary algorithms to be implemented in simulators. In this deliverable, we propose in Section 3.2 a slice-aware downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) resource allocation and admission control strategy based on power optimization and control framework for enabling network slicing with effective isolation in a smart factory network environment, providing simulation results. For those situations where the required power exceeds the available power, an admission control procedure is proposed that includes the selection of the Time Division Multiplexing (TDD) switching point.

In addition, in this deliverable we include a new method, in Section 3.3, for measuring the latency that can be reused in all domains and guarantees good precision and accuracy, as described in the mentioned section.

In (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023) we presented Target Wake Time (TWT) as an alternative to guarantee determinism on Wi-Fi, as well as some initial results on dynamic scheduling. In Section 3.4 we describe the last results of TSN on Wi-Fi. First, two different approaches of using TWT for bounding the latency are presented, including theoretical approaches and a testbed. Also, a novel approach to synchronize reserved windows on Wi-Fi radio frames with TSN periodic traffic is described in this section. Finally, we updated the results regarding dynamic DL/UL splitter and we include a proposal for achieving deterministic communications in roaming scenarios between wireless and wired networks.

In (PREDICT-6G/D2.2, 2023), we introduced an initial implementation of OpenAirInterface (OAI) integrated with other domains, such as Wi-Fi and TSN. In this deliverable, we build upon that foundation by introducing key enhancements to achieve lower and more stable latencies, alongside comprehensive results. In Section 3.5, we provide a comprehensive analysis of mechanisms that can be implemented in a commercial 3GPP network to achieve deterministic multi-domain communications.

3.2 Dynamic scheduling with mixed traffic classes

We propose a slice-aware DL and UL resource allocation and admission control strategy based on optimization and control framework for enabling network slicing with effective isolation in a smart factory network environment in OFDMA access (see Figure 3-1). We consider also the optimization of the switching point between DL and UL as a result of a time division duplexing (TDD) of links. The main contributions are as follows:

- Dynamically allocate DL and UL radio resources such as power and subchannels to mixed traffic type users while prioritizing their unique Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. We model these problems by minimizing transmit power under rates constraints.
- Significantly reduce the complexity of the optimization problem formulation by translating all QoS constraints to target rate constraints. This translation allows for an efficient use of convex optimization algorithms, unlike in (Korrai et al., 2020) and (Kasgari and Saad, 2018).
- Ensure slice isolation, close form target rate expressions for flows in the Ultra-reliable low-latency communication and Time Sensitive slices.
- Proposal of reduced complexity pre-emption admission control strategy and flexible time division duplexing.

Figure 3-1 Subchannel allocation of user flows in OFDMA scheduling

Traffic requirements into transmission rates

We classify flows into three slice types depending on their specific application and the type of traffic they generate. Many smart factories use cases generate traffic that can be accommodated in these slice categories (3GPP TR 22.804, 2020) (5G-ACIA, 2019):

1. **Capacity limited (CL) slices.** In these slices, only the total capacity of the slice matters, designated for best-effort (BE) traffic where the network does not provide any guarantee on the delivery, timing, or sequencing of packets. Smart factory applications such as file sharing, non-critical monitoring data, and web browsing, are classed in the CL slice. Multiple flows of this traffic type can be accommodated using available, non-committed resources, as long as their combined data rate remains below the specified slice capacity limit, C_s .
2. **Ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) slices.** This type of traffic applies to applications such as Augmented Reality, real-time control of robots and machinery, Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV), and real-time surveillance/security systems with stringent requirements on latency, jitter, J , and reliability. This is typically asynchronous traffic characterized by a target outage delay given by $\Pr\{D_i > D_i^{max}\} < 1 - \gamma_i$ (where γ_i and D_i^{max} are the target reliability and the maximum allowable delay respectively) and J as the maximum value for jitter, for a flow i in a URLLC slice. Given an arrival bitrate a_i for the i -th flow the relation of $\Pr\{D_i > D_i^{max}\}$ to the required $r_{o,i}$ for exponential traffic model is :

$$r_{o,i} = a_i + \max(J^{-1}, -\ln(1 - \gamma_i)/D_i^{max}) \quad \forall i \in N_s, \forall s \in S_T.$$

3. **Time sensitive (TS) slices.** These slices cater to applications that demand immediate responses, such as machine vision systems or predictive maintenance. They are designed to handle periodically generated isochronous short packets that must be served upon arrival at the queue, with a target maximum bit error rate (BER). Typically, these packets arrive at periodic intervals that are multiples of the scheduling period T_{sp} , with a fixed packet size L_i . Having this in mind, the transmission rate of flow i in a TS slice is given by:

$$r_{o,i} = L_i/T_{sp}, \forall i \in N_s, \forall s \in S_T.$$

The network must allocate power and subchannels required for network slicing in a manner that satisfies the QoS requirements of all slice types while ensuring their complete isolation in a dynamic network environment. Slicing could be defined in several ways when considering the wireless segment of a network:

- **Subchannel and power coupling.** Isolation is guaranteed on the solution to every optimization problem: a new flow should not increase power beyond the maximum available. This is the approach followed in this document. Subchannel and power coupling, and CL flows have a sum rate limitation rather than a per flow limitation.

- **Subchannel isolation, power coupling.** Fix a number of subchannels for each one of the slices (associated to BE, URLLC, etc.), and then optimize per-flow subchannel allocation and TX power under a single optimization problem. To guarantee isolation, new flows should not increase the power beyond the total maximum available.
- **Subchannel and power isolation.** Fix a maximum transmitted power and a maximum number of subchannel for each one of the slices (associated to BE, URLLC, etc.), and then optimize the per-flow subchannel and transmit power using two optimization problems (since now slices are not coupled). To guarantee isolation, new flows on each slice should not increase the power beyond the maximum available on the slice.

Clearly the latter two will be less optimal (they are more constrained) than the approach we are following in the following, where we have complete freedom of allocation of subchannel and power.

DL scheduling

Consider the DL of an OFDMA cellular network featuring a set K of K available subchannels. The setup consists of a single base station (BS) serving a set N of N flows associated to a number of User Equipment (UE). Each flow associated to the UE has its own, individual rate, reliability, and latency requirements. Initially we do not make assumptions on the packet arrival or the packet length of each flow. For sufficiently large packets, the DL transmission rate from the BS to the user i in a Gaussian channel can be approximated by Shannon's formula, that includes a Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) penalty gap δ_i accounting for the SNR value required to achieve a certain packet error rate:

$$r_i = B \sum_{j=1}^K x_{ij} \log_2 \left(1 + \delta_i \frac{p_{ij} h_{ij}}{x_{ij} \sigma^2} \right)$$

where B is the subchannel bandwidth, h_{ij} is the time-varying channel power gain of the transmission from BS to the flow i on its associated UE, on subchannel j at time slot t , and σ^2 is the noise power. p_{ij} is the DL transmission power of the BS on subchannel j to flow i at slot t . There is a maximum transmitted power p_{max}^{DL} that will impose a limitation in the number of flows that can be accepted in the scheduling of DL flows. x_{ij} is the subchannel allocation indicator with $x_{ij} = 1$ when subchannel j is allocated to flow i at time slot t , otherwise $x_{ij} = 0$. Finally, δ_i is a factor required to get a tight bound on the coded BER for an MQAM modulation associated to flow i (Chung, Vishwanath and Goldsmith, 2001). The rate equation is jointly convex in p_{ij} and x_{ij} .

We take the approach of considering constant channel gains over the scheduling period and map the reliability constraint into a target rate constraint. We minimize the instantaneous transmitted with instantaneous rate constraints as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{p,x} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij}, \\
 & \text{s.t. } r_i \geq r_{o,i}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N} \\
 & \quad p_{ij} \geq 0, x_{ij} \in \{0,1\}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K} \\
 & \quad \sum_{i=1}^N x_{ij} \leq 1, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}.
 \end{aligned}$$

As the problem is convex except for the binarization of x_{ij} , we adopt the conventional approach of relaxing the variables and apply the KKT conditions. We solve the dual variables λ_i associated to the rate constraints using subgradient ellipsoid algorithm and the values for primal values are

$$p_{ij}^* = x_{ij} \left[\frac{\lambda_i B}{\ln 2} - \frac{\sigma^2}{h_{ij}} \right]^+$$

and allocating the user per subchannel as the one minimizing the Lagrangian function, which reads as:

$$i^* = \operatorname{argmin}_i \left\{ \lambda_i^* B \log_2 \left(1 + p_{ij}^* \frac{h_{ij}}{\sigma^2} \right) - p_{ij}^* \right\}$$

UL scheduling

The near-far problem is well known in the UL transmissions: if all terminals transmitted the same power, far users' signals would be swamped by the transmissions of the nearby users at the AD converters of the UL receiver. More precisely, as there is a need of limiting the amplitude of received signals, far users would be more affected by the quantization noise than users close to the BS. One way to solve the issue is to enforce that all UE are received with the same SNR, γ , that is, having an effective power control. Let us rewrite the problem as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{\gamma, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}} \gamma \\
 & \text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{j=1}^K h_{ij} p_{ij} \leq \gamma \cdot \sigma^2, \forall i \in \mathcal{N} \\
 & \quad \quad r_i \geq r_{o,i}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N} \\
 & \quad \quad \sum_{i=1}^N x_{ij} \leq 1, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}. \\
 & \quad \quad p_{ij} \geq 0, x_{ij} \in \{0,1\}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}
 \end{aligned}$$

A convex problem that can be solved by applying the KKT conditions.

Rate adjustment and admission control of flows

If the required transmit power is above the maximum available, how to drop flows or decrease their rate constraints? We will use the information conveyed by the Lagrangian multipliers: those flows with the highest λ will mostly affect the transmitted power when reducing its demanded rate $r_{o,i}$. As a practical rule, the rate of best-effort flows in the CL slice will be curtailed with the sum rate limitation preserved. This should be applied until a single user is allowed in the CL slice. If further power restriction needed, the asynchronous flows should follow.

For the **rate adjustment in the DL**, it is necessary to readjust the target rates of flows in the CL slices to ensure that high-priority tasks in the URLLC and TS slices continue without interruption. Each flow is associated with a Lagrange multiplier, λ_i during optimization which how much the overall power consumption will change if the rate constraints are relaxed or tightened. We propose a rate readjustment strategy (Muñoz, 2011) to readjust the target rates across flows in the CL slices using their multipliers and keep the sum rate of the slice unchanged.

According to chapter 5.6.3 in (Boyd, 2004), the derivative of the optimum value with respect to the constraint is given by the multiplier. Let us call p the sum of powers in the DL, so we can write the total differential as

$$dp^* = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_c} \frac{\partial p^*}{\partial r_{o,i}} dr_{o,i} + \sum_{i \notin \mathcal{S}_c} \frac{\partial p^*}{\partial r_{o,i}} dr_{o,i}$$

where \mathcal{S}_c denotes the set of flows associated to the CL slice. If approximating the differentials by increments, we can write:

$$\Delta p^* \approx \sum_{i \in \mathcal{S}_c} \lambda_i^* \Delta r_{o,i}$$

where we have assumed that the rates of flows outside the CL slices are not being reduced, so for them $\Delta r_{o,i} = 0$. As the target function is convex with respect to the constraints, the rate reduction algorithm may adopt the Newton-Raphson method (Süli, 2003) to iteratively calculate the difference between available and required power based on λ^* , and reduce rates step by step.

Let us rank the CL flows by the value of their associated multiplier, being λ_1 the largest and $\lambda_{|\mathcal{S}_c|}$ the least. We want the total transmitted power to be below p_{max} , and the sum of final rates to remain unchanged. If we decide to reduce the transmission rate of the flow having the largest multiplier, we will reduce the most the transmitted power. On its turn, to maintain the total rate, we will have to redistribute the transmission rate among the rest of CL flows. Therefore, we will take the following expressions at the n -th iteration of the algorithm:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta p^* &= p_n - p_{max} \\ \Delta r_{o,1} &= r_{o,1n} - r_{o,1n+1} = \beta_n \quad \beta_n > 0 \\ \Delta r_{o,i} &= r_{o,i n} - r_{o,i n+1} = -\frac{\beta_n}{|\mathcal{S}_c| - 1} \quad \forall i > 1 \end{aligned}$$

The reduction of rate at step n is obtained as:

$$\beta_n = \frac{p_n - p_{max}}{\lambda_1 - \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}_c| - 1} \sum_{i=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} \lambda_i}$$

Using these values, we update the rates of CL flows as:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{o,1 n+1} &= \max(r_{o,1 n} - \beta_n, 0) \\ r_{o,i n+1} &= r_{o,i n} + \frac{\min(\beta_n, r_{o,1 n})}{|\mathcal{S}_c| - 1} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_c \setminus 1 \end{aligned}$$

and recompute the required total transmitted power p_{n+1} by solving the optimization algorithm again. The adjustments continue until power consumption $p_n \leq p_{max}$, managed by a tolerance value. Note that the algorithm could be easily adapted if we decided to reduce the rate of the $M > 1$ flows with largest λ , or using other redistribution of rates across flows. Note also that the

algorithm automatically drops flows if the rate reduction required is below the current rate. The detailed algorithm is described in Figure 3-2.

Algorithm Rate Readjustment Algorithm with Sum Rate Preserve for the CL slice

- 1: **Input:** $r_{o,i} \forall i \in \mathcal{N}_s, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}_c, \epsilon$ and p_{max}
- 2: **Output:** $r_{o,i} \forall i \in \mathcal{N}_s, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}_c$, and p_{ij}
- 3: **Solve** the DL optimization problem, get p_{ij}, λ
- 4: **Sort** flows in descending order of λ_i
- 5: **Evaluate** $p = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}$
- 6: **while** $p > p_{max} - \epsilon$ **do**
- 7: $\beta = \frac{p - p_{max}}{\lambda_1 - \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}_c| - 1} \sum_{i=2}^{|\mathcal{S}_c|} \lambda_i}$
- 8: $r_{o,1} \leftarrow \max(r_{o,1} - \beta n, 0)$
- 9: $r_{o,i} \leftarrow r_{o,i} + \frac{\min(\beta n, r_{o,1} n)}{|\mathcal{S}_c| - 1}, \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_c \setminus 1$
- 10: **Solve** the DL optimization problem, get p_{ij}, λ
- 11: **Sort** flows in descending order of λ_i
- 12: **Evaluate** $p = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}$
- 13: **end while**

Figure 3-2 Rate adjustment algorithm for the DL with sum rate preserve for the CL slice.

For the **rate adjustment in the UL**, the stressing situation comes from a UE requiring more transmit power than its maximum available. In this case, we need to consider reducing service for the best effort flows first, even if associated to non-power limited UE: once their rates have been reduced, optimizing the UL resource allocation problem will free some subchannels that can be used by the power-limited UE, who on its turn can reduce the transmit power and still achieve the target rates of its associated flows.

Now, the relation between the rate of a certain flow i and the associated transmitted power is captured by the multiplier of the optimization problem, but the relation can still be computed from the Shannon equation where all SC are allocated the same power:

$$\tilde{\lambda}_i = \frac{\partial p_i^*}{\partial r_{o,i}} = \frac{\ln 2}{B} \left(\sum_j \frac{h_{ij}}{\sigma^2 + p h_{ij}} \right)^{-1} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{S}_c$$

and the summation applies to the set of SC allocated to the i -th flow. We will sort the values of in descending order, reduce the rate in an amount β and solve the UL problem again until the transmitted power of the affected user gets below its maximum. The previous algorithm applies also here.

Time division duplexing split

In flexible TDD systems, UL and DL transmissions are separated in time, allowing the time division between them to be adjusted dynamically to meet varying traffic demands. This enables the system to adapt to changing traffic patterns and optimize resource allocation. Assume the time allocated to the DL is a fraction η (conversely, $1 - \eta$ for the UL) of time. We consider a single BS deployment, like an in closed industrial venue, and hence the switching point selection does not generate DL-to-UL interference. The rate constraint in the definition of the DL scheduling problem read as:

$$r_i^{DL} \geq r_{o,i}^{DL} / \eta^{DL}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$$

The flexibility of resource allocation allows rebalancing between UL and DL whenever one link is power-limited while the other is not. Rather than reducing transmission rates or dropping flows, it is more spectrally efficient to grant more transmission time to the power-limited link. Rate reduction or flow drops are reserved for situations where both links are power-limited, or when transferring transmission time is insufficient to resolve the issue.

Let us derive a practical criterion to adjust η by evaluating how much a change in η impacts on the required power for the power-limited link. Take $p^{DL*}(\eta)$ as the optimum value of power for the DL and assume it is larger than the maximum transmission power available. According to chapter 5.6.3 in (Boyd, 2004), the derivative of the optimum value with respect to the constraint is given by the multiplier, in our case associated to the transmission rate:

$$\frac{\partial p^{DL*}(\eta)}{\partial (r_{o,i}^{DL} / \eta)} = \lambda_i^{DL*}$$

Using the partial differential

$$\partial (r_{o,i}^{DL} / \eta) = -\frac{r_{o,i}^{DL}}{\eta^2} \partial \eta$$

and the total differential for p^{DL*} we obtain:

$$dp^{DL*}(\eta) = -\frac{1}{\eta^2} \sum_i r_{o,i}^{DL} \lambda_i^{DL*} d\eta$$

Differentials are replaced approximately by increments so that we can iteratively update the value of η following an iterative Newton-Raphson algorithm:

$$\Delta p^{DL*} = p_n^{DL} - p_{max}^{DL}$$

$$\Delta \eta = \eta_n - \eta_{n+1} = \frac{-(p_n^{DL} - p_{max}^{DL})\eta^2}{\sum_i r_{o,i}^{DL} \lambda_i^{DL}}$$

Likewise, if limitation in the transmitted power is found in the UL, and with $(1 - \eta)$ in the rate constraint in the UL:

$$r_i^{UL} \geq r_{o,i}^{UL}/(1 - \eta), \forall i \in N.$$

the total differential for p^{UL*} is:

$$dp^{UL*}(\eta) = \frac{1}{(1 - \eta)^2} \sum_i r_{o,i}^{UL} \lambda_i^{UL*} d\eta$$

Again, differentials are approximated by increments so that we can iteratively update the value of η following an iterative Newton-Raphson algorithm:

$$\Delta p^{UL*} = p_n^{UL} - p_{max}^{UL}$$

$$\Delta \eta = \eta_n - \eta_{n+1} = \frac{(p_n^{UL} - p_{max}^{UL})(1 - \eta)^2}{\sum_i r_{o,i}^{UL} \lambda_i^{UL}}$$

It may naturally be the case that the adjustment of η is not enough to accommodate the required transmission rates. In that case, we must resort to the reduction of rates of flows, or eventually to dropping the most power-demanding flows, as described in previous section.

Therefore, in

Figure 3-3 we propose a fast algorithm that selects the value of η iteratively.

Simulations

For our simulation, we consider an indoor smart factory environment, characterized by densely packed reflecting elements of diverse shapes and sizes. The area considered is a closed building of 97m x 36m, as displayed in Figure 3-4, where UE are positioned for simulation results of the OFDMA resource allocation. Multiple flows (on each of CL, URLLC and TS slices) are associated to multiple UE, with different QoS requirements that generate different traffic patterns. We consider a single omnidirectional 5G BS positioned in the center of the area. For channel generation we use channel traces obtained from SIRADEL's ray-tracing tool for random

positions of UE in some of the 850 positions in a grid of 2m resolution. Each user is moving along a linear trajectory between two points in the grid.

Algorithm	TDD Time Split Adjustment Algorithm
1:	Input: $r_{o,i} \forall i \in \mathcal{N}$, ϵ , η and $p_{max}^{DL}, p_{max}^{UL}$
2:	Output: $r_{o,i}$, and $p_{ij} \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \eta$
3:	Solve DL problem in (17), get $p_{ij}^{DL}, \lambda^{DL}$
4:	Solve UL problem in (35), get $p_{ij}^{UL}, \lambda^{UL}$
5:	Evaluate $p^{DL} = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}^{DL}$, $p^{UL} = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}^{UL}$ % DL is power limited, adjust time split
6:	while $p^{DL} > p_{max}^{DL} - \epsilon$ and $p^{UL} < p_{max}^{UL} - \epsilon$ do
7:	$\eta \leftarrow \eta + \frac{(p_{max}^{DL} - p^{DL})\eta^2}{\sum_i r_{o,i}^{DL} \lambda_i^{DL}}$
8:	Solve DL problem with $r_{o,i}^{DL}/\eta$, get $p_{ij}^{DL}, \lambda^{DL}$
9:	Solve UL problem with $r_{o,i}^{UL}/(1-\eta)$, get $p_{ij}^{UL}, \lambda^{UL}$
10:	Evaluate $p^{DL} = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}^{DL}$, $p^{UL} = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}^{UL}$
11:	end while % If adjusting time split is not enough
12:	if $p^{DL} > p_{max}^{DL} - \epsilon$ and $p^{UL} = p_{max}^{UL} - \epsilon$ then
13:	Adjust DL rates using algorithm 5
14:	end if % UL is power limited, adjust time split
15:	while $p^{DL} < p_{max}^{DL} - \epsilon$ and $p^{UL} > p_{max}^{UL} - \epsilon$ do
16:	$\eta \leftarrow \eta - \frac{(p^{UL} - p_{max}^{UL})(1-\eta)^2}{\sum_i r_{o,i}^{DL} \lambda_i^{UL}}$
17:	Solve DL problem with $r_{o,i}^{DL}/\eta$, get $p_{ij}^{DL}, \lambda^{DL}$
18:	Solve UL problem with $r_{o,i}^{UL}/(1-\eta)$, get $p_{ij}^{UL}, \lambda^{UL}$
19:	Evaluate $p^{DL} = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}^{DL}$, $p^{UL} = \sum_{i,j} p_{ij}^{UL}$
20:	end while % If adjusting time split is not enough
21:	if $p^{UL} > p_{max}^{UL} - \epsilon$ and $p^{DL} = p_{max}^{DL} - \epsilon$ then
22:	Adjust UL rates using algorithm 5
23:	end if % Both UL & DL are power limited
24:	if $p^{UL} > p_{max}^{UL} - \epsilon$ and $p^{DL} > p_{max}^{DL} - \epsilon$ then
25:	Adjust UL and DL rates using algorithm 5

Figure 3-3 Time split adjustment algorithm for TDD duplexing with rate adjustment

Figure 3-4 A factory building environment where UE can be positioned on the red dots and the gNB is placed on the cyan symbol in center of the area

Table 3-1 shows the link parameters assumed for our simulations.

Table 3-1 Link level simulation parameters

Parameters	Values
Carrier frequency, f_c	3.7 GHz
Antenna gains	$G_{gNB} = 6$ dBi $G_{UE} = 0$ dBi
Transmit power in DL	23 dBm
Noise spectral density	-174 dBm/Hz
Total bandwidth, BW	25 MHz
Subchannel bandwidth, B	180 kHz
Subcarrier spacing	15 kHz, numerology 0
Number of subchannels	106
Cell radius	150 m

Also, the QoS specifications per slice, and the number of active flows in each slice is shown in Table 3-2. We assume that all flows in the URLLC and TS slices have the same QoS specifications.

Table 3-2 Specifications of traffic: slice types, quality-of-service and number of active flows

Slice type	Requirements	Target Rates	No. of active flows at frame t		
			t<300	600≤t≤900	t>900
CL	$C_s = 27$ Mbps	27 Mbps	5	3	8
URLLC	$J_s = 1$ ms $\gamma_s = 99.9\%$ $a_s = 2$ Mbps $D_{s,max} = 10$ ms	2 Mbps	2	1	3
TS	$L = 5$ kB $T_{sp} = 10$ ms	1.64 Mbps	1	1	1

At time slots 300 and 600, we simulate a sudden decrease and increase, respectively, in the number of flows in the CL slice. We assume one scheduling period of 10 ms. The total simulation run time is 900 time slots. Flows are disappearing and appearing at scheduling periods 300 and 600. Users are linearly moving between two random points in the 2D grid, so the required transmitted power is changing over time depending on the number of users and their trajectories with respect to the gNodeB (gNB) (see Figure 3-5).

From the power allocation it can be checked that the Equal Power Allocation (EPA) generates a power excess of <2.5 dB as compared to the Optimal Power Allocation (OPA) allocation. At the first stages of the scheduling, user 8 is the most deprived user, requiring the highest number of SC. Over time, the number of users change from 8 to 5 and 12, and their positions change. The required power and the allocation of SC change accordingly so that in all cases their target transmission rates are preserved.

In this section we have shown that a simple resource allocation and admission control procedure can be defined for mixed traffic in OFDMA access both in DL and UL. The optimization procedure also provides the elements required to allocate the switching time for UL and DL transmission in a TDD duplexing system in a deployment of a single gNB. The extension to multiple gNB for interference avoidance between UL and DL is deferred to D2.4 together with L1/L2 system level simulations that will shed light on the number of flows a simulated dynamic industrial deployment may satisfy as compared to a TDMA system.

Figure 3-5 Initial (top figure) and final (middle figure) subchannel allocation. Total transmitted power for the DL using equal power allocation (EPA) and the optimal power allocation (OPA) (bottom figure).

3.3 Flexible latency evaluation method

In this section, a methodology for real-time network latency measurement is introduced. This technique is designed to supply accurate and up-to-date network performance data, enabling informed decision-making for both system control mechanisms and digital twin simulations. This flexible latency measurement method is engineered to continuously monitor network load and provide immediate, real-time data to both the control plane for quick decision-making and/or to a Digital Twin (DT) for ongoing analysis and simulation. Its primary function is to assess the latency between two network nodes, delivering data with varying levels of precision based on the hardware capabilities of the nodes involved. Specifically, if the nodes are synchronized, the tool can capture one-way latency; however, when synchronization isn't available, it defaults to calculating the Round Trip Time (RTT).

Main Components

- **Sender Node:** The sender node is tasked with creating and dispatching probe packets along the network path being tested. These probe packets are User Datagram Protocol (UDP) packets with a payload containing essential information for gathering network statistics. For instance, the Echo-Receiver has to capture timestamping data that the sender can later retrieve for analysis.
- **Echo-Receiver Node:** Operating as an echo server, the receiver node's role is to accept incoming probe packets from the sender and send them back. This exchange enables accurate latency measurement by recording timestamps at each stage.

As illustrated in Figure 3-6, the Sender transmits UDP packets, recording a transmission timestamp (Tx timestamp) at the hardware level, if Network Interface Card (NIC) timestamping is supported, or, otherwise, at the kernel level. The Echo-Receiver, in turn, records a reception timestamp (Rx timestamp) upon receiving the packets. Then it sends back another UDP packet with the Rx timestamping and the Tx stamping of the previous packet. About this last point: it is worth noting how, on the Echo Receiver, the Tx timestamping is captured on the transmitted packet, but this information can be sent to the Sender only in the payload of the next packet.

By capturing these timestamps at both transmission and reception points, the tool can deliver precise latency measurements, adjusted according to the available timestamping capabilities.

Figure 3-6 Schema of the tool

The tool currently offers the following parameters for tuning:

- The generation period for the probe packets.
- The size of the UDP payload

Level of precision

The latency measurement tool is designed to support various levels of timestamping precision, adapting to the capabilities of the available hardware on each node. This adaptability allows for flexible deployment across a range of network environments, from those with high-precision NICs capable of hardware timestamping to simpler setups relying on software-based timestamps. By leveraging these different methods, the tool ensures reliable latency measurements across networks with varying levels of sophistication and synchronization.

Hardware Timestamping: when hardware timestamping is available on the NIC, the tool achieves an exceptional level of precision, often within tens of nanoseconds. Hardware timestamping records the exact moment a packet enters or leaves the network interface, directly in the NIC hardware, which reduces delays and processing variability. This level of precision is ideal for high-performance applications that require fine-grained latency analysis such as in real-time communications, where every nanosecond counts.

Software Timestamping: in cases where hardware timestamping is not available, the tool defaults to software timestamping, where timestamps are applied within the operating system's kernel. While software timestamping is less precise—typically accurate within tens of microseconds—it is still sufficient for many applications that do not require nanosecond-level accuracy, for example on a long-distance communication path. Software timestamping

allows for broader deployment in less demanding environments, providing a solution without requiring specialized NICs or hardware upgrades.

Synchronization between nodes: synchronization between nodes plays a key role in determining the type of latency measurement possible. When nodes are time-synchronized (e.g., through protocols like Precision Time Protocol (PTP), or Network Time Protocol), the tool can measure one-way latency, which captures the delay from the Sender to the Echo Receiver only or on the other direction. This measurement is highly valuable for identifying asymmetries in network paths or pinpointing specific delays within one direction of communication.

However, if the nodes are not synchronized, the tool defaults to measuring RTT, which assesses the total delay for a packet to travel from the sender to the receiver and back. While RTT provides a useful overview of latency, it is less granular than one-way latency and does not allow for the identification of direction-specific delays.

By incorporating these three dimensions of precision and synchronization, the latency measurement tool is adaptable to various network configurations and use cases. One of the testbeds that will be used is the TWT Wireless Network described in Section 3.4.1.2.. This tool is suitable for supplying real-time data to the PREDICT-6G control plane and/or DT.

Distributed architecture

Nodes can act as both Sender and Echo-receiver simultaneously, which is particularly useful for stressing different paths in a network from various sources. This dual functionality allows for more comprehensive network testing and analysis.

For instance, to evaluate how the network performs in connecting different slices, multiple instances of a Sender software module can run on the same physical node with different configurations (e.g., rate and payload size). These instances can interact with different Echo-receiver nodes, collecting multiple measurements concurrently.

This approach enables testing of multiple network paths simultaneously and a more comprehensive analysis of network behavior under various conditions.

Figure 3-7 illustrates the software architecture of each physical node in a distributed scenario. In this setup, one node (e.g., the one on the left) can run multiple instances of the "Sender" module and one instance of the "Echo-receiver" module, while other nodes can act as simple echo-receiver nodes.

Figure 3-7 Software architecture on nodes

To further support a distributed approach, each node acting as a Sender is also equipped with additional software elements:

- A database that collects all measurements from the sender instances
- An API server that makes the data available to external entities for data analysis and other purposes

The local database collects every measurement related to tested network paths originating from the node itself. This continuous data availability allows the API server to provide real-time analysis, such as "the average RTT towards node A in the last 10 minutes" or "the maximum latency for connections towards nodes B and C." By combining these dynamic measurements with the Sender modules' configuration information, this distributed architecture offers both detailed and aggregated evaluations of overall network performance.

The flexibility of an API server that responds to simple API requests can be leveraged to build high-level monitoring applications. These applications can run on a different general-purpose node and be easily integrated with other entities in the overall Predict architecture.

As an illustrative example, Figure 3-8 showcases a Dashboard displaying real-time moving average of RTT measurements between two pairs of nodes in the test network. Several Intel NUCs serve as senders and echo-receivers. Green lines indicate the direction of probing packets, while blue lines represent the flow of statistical data towards the dashboard node.

Figure 3-8 Test network (left) and live RTT monitoring in a dashboard (right)

3.4 TSN on Wi-Fi

In (PREDICT-6G/D2.2, 2023), we presented expressions that, leveraging Network Calculus, model the queues of Wi-Fi devices supporting 802.11ax OFDMA and rTWT.

In this section, we first present how the Target Wake Time, and, in particular, its enhancement restricted TWT (rTWT), can be used to ensure deterministic channel access in the Wi-Fi domain. A testbed has also been developed to demonstrate the advantages this mechanism can bring in terms of access delay and energy consumption. Then, we present a new approach that aims to reduce the amount of radio resources required to support TSN flows over a wireless link, while guaranteeing a maximum delay and zero jitter. Additionally, we define an upper-level scheduler to be run at the Wi-Fi AP that dynamically decides the time allocated for UL and DL transmissions. Finally, we focus on the Multi-Link Operation (MLO) feature of Wi-Fi 7 and

leverage it to achieve deterministic communication and seamless mobility in a hybrid network using both Wi-Fi 7 and Ethernet.

Following the approach in Section 3.4.1, we again assume that the AP organizes transmissions in the time domain. Based on this assumption, Section 3.4.2 presents an entirely new contribution that explores how much transmission windows can be compacted in the wireless link while introducing minimal excess delay and zero jitter. The key idea is to overlap the windows of adjacent flows by leveraging statistical knowledge of the stations' time-varying transmission rates. The achievable gains in terms of throughput and reduced control cycle are presented at the end of the section for a typical industrial scenario operated with 802.11ax PHY-compliant stations.

In deliverable (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023) a hierarchical/modular approach was introduced for the scheduling within the Wireless Node at the AP as was shown in Figure 11 of (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023). This approach involved an upper-level scheduler, also named DL/UL splitter, that dynamically decides the allocation of time for UL and DL transmissions, following the setup defined in Section 3.4.2. Once the decision regarding the allocation of resources to UL and DL is made, the next scheduling levels, i.e., the UL and DL schedulers, operate independently. The upper-level scheduler for the allocation of time to DL/UL outlined in (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023) was initially implemented on a 5G wireless link. In Section 3.4.3 of this current deliverable, we introduce new DL/UL splitters –both custom-designed and reinforcement learning-based– and apply them to a Wi-Fi link, presenting the corresponding simulation results.

In Section 3.4.4, we delve into the Multi-Link Operation (MLO) feature of Wi-Fi 7, utilizing it to achieve deterministic communication and seamless mobility within a hybrid network that incorporates both Wi-Fi 7 and Ethernet. Our proposed approach has been implemented and tested using the ns3 simulator. It involves training an AI model to predict Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as latency, Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), and Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), as well as to classify the connections between a Multi-Link Device (MLD) mobile station (STAs) and two fixed MLDs Access Points (APs). Consequently, handover is executed based on the classification of these KPI predictions, ensuring it is scheduled at the optimal moment to guarantee continuous communication.

3.4.1 TWT for deterministic channel access

Target Wake Time is a new Wi-Fi feature introduced in the 802.11ax amendment (IEEE 802.11ax, 2021). TWT-compatible stations can stipulate agreements on wake and sleep time periods. During a sleep period a station can “doze”, by turning off its transceiver to save energy. Any traffic destined to the dozing station is buffered at the sender until a wake period (technically called TWT Service Period) begins. Then, at the target wake time, the dozing state ends: the station activates its transceiver, and the traffic exchange begins. Besides allowing for low-power network operation, TWT can also be used to enable Time-division multiple access in Wi-Fi. If only one station is active at a time, then channel contention is avoided, and traffic can be exchanged with more deterministic delays.

Below, we first present how to leverage an enhanced version of TWT, namely, the restricted TWT, and then we describe the TWT-based testbed we developed to demonstrate the effectiveness of TWT in terms of both deterministic channel access and energy savings.

3.4.1.1 Exploiting rTWT: The PONTE solution

The 802.11be amendment introduced restricted Target Wake Time, an enhanced version of TWT that supports Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) services. In restricted TWT (rTWT), only stations (STAs) associated with the TWT session are permitted to access the channel within the rTWT service period, therefore, the rest of STAs must stop their transmissions before it begins, reducing contention for channel access. Each rTWT session is defined by two main parameters:

- **TWT Wake Interval:** the period of the session.
- **Minimum TWT Wake Duration:** the minimum active duration.

These parameters are established during a negotiation phase between the STAs and the AP (Figure 3-9). The session’s timing and repetition are based on the traffic identifier in the Traffic Info field. It’s important to note that any transmission from STAs participating in an rTWT session must conclude within their designated rTWT periods. Consequently, sessions with longer intervals and durations are more suitable for larger packet transmissions.

Figure 3-9 Depict of OFDMA and rTWT scenario

The PONTE approach utilizes stochastic scaling curves (Wang et al., 2013) and Network Calculus (Le Boudec and Thiran, 2001) to assess the reliability of a real-time Wireless Transmission (rTWT) session, defined as the percentage of packets received successfully within specific delay and jitter constraints, despite packet loss. This reliability boundary is expressed as a polynomial whose sign indicates whether reliability criteria are fulfilled, accounting for factors like packet errors, retransmissions, and multiple priority queues in the STAs. With this polynomial, PONTE schedules OFDMA transmissions across available OFDMA Resource Units (RUs) for multiple STAs. Furthermore, PONTE minimizes jitter by leveraging a playout buffer (see Chapter 9.2 in (Kurose and Ross, 2017)) at the Access Point (AP).

IEEE 802.11ax OFDMA: OFDMA plays a crucial role in supporting time-sensitive traffic. First introduced in the 802.11ax standard (IEEE 802.11ax, 2021), OFDMA enables simultaneous transmissions for multiple STAs by partitioning the channel into groups of subcarriers called RUs (Figure 3-9). The quantity and frequency allocation of RUs are adaptable based on the number of STAs being served. The AP manages medium access by sending Trigger Frames, which map specific RUs to STAs for DL traffic. For UL, an OFDMA frame aggregates all STAs' transmissions in their designated RUs. Although OFDMA builds upon the traditional Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance protocol, the AP can adjust the contention window to guarantee STA transmissions (Khorov et al., 2018).

IEEE 802.1Qbv: Created by the IEEE TSN Task Group (IEEE 802.1 TSN Task group, 2019), IEEE 802.1Qbv specifies scheduled traffic transmission by managing egress queues with gate

control and prioritizing traffic. STAs configure a Gate Control List (GCL), which periodically opens egress queues to allow data exchange. Following the approach in (Barroso et al, 2023), (Cavalcanti et al., 2022), we open these egress gates during rTWT sessions.

Next, we formulate the problem of scheduling time-sensitive traffic with rTWT and 802.11ax OFDMA. For each STA, we determine the adequate rTWT parameters: (i) TWT Wake interval, L_u ; (ii) Minimum TWT wake duration, $L_u + T_u$ and (iii) first session offset δ_u . Additionally, for each OFDMA transmission we must decide which STA/user u is assigned to each RU r , which we denote as $x_{r,u} \in \{0,1\}$.

The decisions $L_u, T_u, \delta_u, x_{u,r}$ must be made such that the delay Δ_q , jitter J_q , and reliability $1 - \varepsilon_q$ constraints are met for the traffic present in each user queue, i.e., $\forall q \in Q_u$. Note ε_q refers to the violation tolerance for both the delay and jitter constraints of traffic in queue q .

Consider STAs/users u with queues Q_u . Each queue $q \in Q_u$ has delay Δ_q , jitter J_q and reliability $1 - \varepsilon_q$ requirements. Decide the RU assignment $x_{u,r}$ and rTWT setup L_u, T_u, δ_u to meet traffic requirements and maximize the scheduling profit.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \max_{x_{u,r}, L_u, T_u, \delta_u} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_u x_{u,r} \cdot p_{u,r} \\
 & s.t. : \sum_u x_{u,r} \cdot \frac{L_u}{T_u + L_u} \leq 1, \quad \forall r \in R \\
 & \quad \mathbb{P}(d_q(t) \leq \Delta_q) \geq 1 - \varepsilon_q, \quad \forall t, u, q \in Q_u \\
 & \quad \mathbb{P}(j_q \leq J_q) \geq 1 - \varepsilon_q, \quad \forall u, q \in Q_u
 \end{aligned}$$

where j_q is the real jitter experienced by queue q and $p_{u,r}$ the profit of assigning user $u \in U$ to RU r .

First constraint ensures that the fraction of time of rTWT sessions does not exceed 100%, while second and third ensure that delay and jitter constraints are met with the given reliability level $1 - \varepsilon_q$.

Note the profit values $p_{u,r}$ are defined by the owner of the Wi-Fi AP device. For example, if STAs/users u, u' have time-sensitive and best effort traffic, respectively, setting $p_{u,r} > p_{u',r}, \forall r$ prioritizes time-sensitive traffic over best effort traffic.

In the following, we demonstrate the above problem is NP-hard. To prove that, we show that it can be an instance of the Generalized Assignment Problem (Kellerer et al., 2004) which is NP-hard (Öncan, 2007).

Consider a problem instance in which the violation tolerance is $\varepsilon_q = 1, \forall q$. Hence, delay and jitter constraints are always met. Assume also that rTWT parameters L_u, T_u, δ_u are given for a sufficiently large number of STAs u_1, \dots, u_M . Also consider that the AP can only split the bandwidth into two RUs r, r' in OFDMA transmissions. Lastly, assume STAs rate requirements are much smaller than that provided by each RU, i.e., $C_r \gg C_q^{Tot}, \forall q$.

Clearly, the solution of the instance detailed above consists in just taking OFDMA decisions $x_{u,r}, \forall u$ to set STAs at either of the RUs, i.e., $x_{r,u} + x_{r',u} \leq 1, \forall u$. Thus, the described instance of the Problem is an instance of the GAP with: STAs/users u as items with weights $\frac{L_u}{L_u + T_u}$; RUs r, r' as bins with capacity 1; and profits $p_{u,r}$.

We then propose PONTE, a solution to previous problem that leverages 802.1Qbv, MU OFDMA transmissions and rTWT. PONTE stands for **P**olynomial-based **N**etwork calculus solution for **T**ime sensitiv**E** traffic. In the following we detail step by step how PONTE solves the problem, a schematic of which is depicted in Figure 3-10.

Figure 3-10 PONTE steps

Step 1: *rTWT/802.1Qbv period specification.* PONTE sets the TWT Wake interval $L_u + T_u$ for every STA u , and fixes the periodicity of 802.1Qbv GCL to match $L_u + T_u$ -- i.e., PONTE aligns rTWT and 802.1Qbv. Specifically, PONTE specifies a common period $L_u + T_u = \mathcal{T} = \min_q \left\{ \frac{\Delta_q}{2} \right\}, \forall u$ that is half the strictest delay requirement among all time-sensitive flows.

Step 2: *ensure rTWT reliability.* PONTE finds the adequate stochastic scaling curves $S^{\varepsilon_q}(\pi)$ to ensure the rTWT reliability meets the requirement $1 - \varepsilon_q$ of every queue q .

Hence, PONTE sets $\hat{\varepsilon}_q$ of the stochastic scaling curve to ensure the rTWT reliability is greater than/equal to the time-sensitive reliability requirement, i.e., it sets

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_q = 1 + \log_N \frac{1 - \varepsilon_q}{1 - p^{N+1}}$$

Step 3: *rTWT/802.1Qbv session duration.* Third, PONTE specifies the rTWT Minimum TWT wake duration L_u and sets the same value for 802.1Qbv GCL gate opening time. In particular, PONTE selects $L_u, \forall u$ to meet the delay requirement Δ_u .

PONTE takes the stochastic scaling curve $S^{\hat{\varepsilon}_q}(\pi)$ of the previous step; sets the 1st rTWT session offset $\delta_u = T_u, \forall u$; and looks for a session duration L_u to satisfy inequality $h(\alpha_q^{(Tot)}, \beta_q^*) \leq \Delta_q$. From previous results, we know $h(\alpha_q^{(Tot)}, \beta_q^*)$ is fully determined except for the rTWT rate for user u , i.e., $R_u = \frac{C_r L_u}{L_u + T_u}$ with C_r the rate of each RU. Hence, PONTE looks for the smallest rate R_u to satisfy the delay requirement. It transforms the delay inequality into a polynomial $p(R_u, \delta_u)$ whose sign determines whether the delay requirement is met.

Given $\delta_u = T_u$, we know $p(R_u, \delta_u)$ is a polynomial of degree $N + 1$ on R_u . From empirical evidence, we observe that $p(R_u, T_u)$ is monotonically increasing for any value of $R_u \leq C_r$ satisfying the stability constraint (the rate R_u must be enough to dispatch the aggregated arrival rate of all its queues), i.e., for any value in the interval

$$A = \left(\sum_{q'} C_{q'}^{(Tot)} + C_q \sum_i^N p^i, C_r \right).$$

Using Rolle's theorem, polynomial $p(R_u, T_u)$ has a single root $R_{u,0} \in A$, and PONTE runs Brent's method (Brent, 2013) to find it. Finally, it takes the computed root to obtain the Minimum TWT wake duration:

$$L_u = \frac{R_{u,0} T_u}{C_r}.$$

Step 4: *802.11 OFDMA scheduling.* PONTE assigns which RU r is used by each user u in OFDMA transmissions -- i.e., PONTE sets $x_{u,r}$. To decide the OFDMA scheduling $x_{u,r}$, it reduces the problem to the GAP -- as specified previously. That is, PONTE creates a GAP instance with user-defined profits $p_{u,r}$; bins (RUs) of capacity 1; and item (STAs) weights $\frac{L_u}{T}$ -- with L_u obtained as detailed in the previous step.

To solve the GAP, PONTE leverages the FPTAS proposed in (Lawler, 1979) dynamic programming approach that sequentially solves the single knapsack problem using the FPTAS Lawler algorithm (Lawler, 1979). Concretely, it invokes (Cohen, Katzir and Raz, 2006) repeatedly until no item (STA) assignment is found or all items are assigned. As a result, it specifies the OFDMA scheduling $x_{u,r}$ of every STA/user u .

Step 5: *jitter mitigation.* Lastly, PONTE checks whether the jitter requirement is met. By construction, PONTE election of $L_u, T_u, \delta_u, x_{u,r}$ fully determines the delay CDF $F_{d(t)}(x) = \mathbb{P}(d(t) \leq x)$. Consequently, it is possible to obtain the average (Tijms, 1994) and its standard deviation j_q (jitter) (Kurose et Ross, 2017) with the density function $f_{d(t)}(x) = \frac{d}{dx} F_{d(t)}(x)$. If the computed jitter j_q is stricter than the requirement J_q , PONTE passes the received traffic from queue q to a playout buffer that dispatches packets at a rate that matches the packet period, i.e., $\frac{l_{max}^q}{c_q}$ seconds. PONTE meets the jitter requirement with probability $1 - \varepsilon_q$ since the playout buffer guarantees¹ a zero-delay variance between two packets with probability $1 - \varepsilon_q$.

Thanks to the GAP reduction from Step 5, PONTE provides the following guarantees. Denote ϵ as the granularity of Lawler's algorithm, R as the number of RUs, and U the number of STAs to schedule. PONTE scheduler is an FPTAS algorithm with $(2 + \epsilon)$ -approximation guarantee, and $\mathcal{O}\left(R^2 U \log \frac{1}{\epsilon} + \frac{R^2}{\epsilon^4}\right)$ worst case run time.

PONTE complexity is governed by Step 4, in which it solves the OFDMA scheduling problem as the GAP. As specified in Step 4, PONTE repeatedly invokes Lawler (Lawler, 1979) algorithm. Just a single invocation of (Cohen, Katzir and Raz, 2006) guarantees a $(2 + \epsilon)$ -approximation; and a worst-case run time $\mathcal{O}\left(RU \log \frac{1}{\epsilon} + \frac{R^2}{\epsilon^4}\right)$ (Cohen, Katzir and Raz, 2006).

By construction of Algorithm 2 (Cohen, Katzir and Raz, 2006), its result ensures that the bin (RU) has no more room for any item (STA). However, there may be room for more items in the other bins (RUs) e.g., if the dynamic programming approach may have moved an item from the first to the last bin. Hence, PONTE issues, at most, R invocations of (Cohen, Katzir and Raz, 2006) in case it exhausts the capacities of all bins (RUs). Consequently, the worst case run time is $\mathcal{O}\left(R^2 U \log \frac{1}{\epsilon} + \frac{R^2}{\epsilon^4}\right)$

Finally, PONTE guarantees reliability, delay and jitter requirements for time-sensitive traffic by construction of Step 2, 3 and 5 respectively.

We are currently conducting experiments to validate our insights about PONTE. The results of these experiments, along with a detailed analysis, will be included in the next deliverable D2.4.

¹ It is possible to obtain the exact jitter j_q . However, we omit it for brevity given j_q has an order of magnitude of 10^{-18} at the exit of the playout buffer.

3.4.1.2 TWT testbed

To develop, test and validate procedures and algorithms for TWT scheduling, we have designed a dedicated testbed, as depicted in Figure 3-11.

Figure 3-11 Testbed architecture and workflow

The TWT testbed consists of 10 STAs, one AP, and a PC host, as shown in Figure 3-12. The STAs generate traffic towards a PC host. Traffic first reaches the AP, then it is forwarded to the PC host, which is connected to the AP via a wired link for the maximum reliability and minimum delay. To transmit traffic, first each STA has to setup an implicit TWT agreement with the AP according to a predefined schedule. The schedule dictates the periodic non-overlapped TWT SPs that each board has to demand in the TWT setup. Non overlapped TWT SPs allows for isolation in time of the collision domain, which in turn allows for deterministic transmission delays. After the TWT setup, each STA transmits traffic during the designated SP. To inspect the Wi-Fi traffic, the PC host is capable of sniffing the wireless channel.

Readily available commercial components have been selected to replicate a possible real-world Industrial IoT deployment. The STAs are Espressif ESP32-C6-DevKitC-1, low-cost IoT boards that can be purchased for under €10 each. They utilize the ESP32-C6 System on Chip, featuring a 32-bit RISC-V processor with IEEE 802.11ax connectivity (restricted to a 20 MHz channel in the 2.4 GHz band, Single Input Single Output) and support for Individual (i.e., per station) TWT allocation.

The AP is a Synology WRX560, a TWT-compatible 802.11ax router, configured to assign static IP addresses to the STAs. This simplifies the setup, as a single firmware can be flashed onto all STAs, and the desired behavior of each STA (such as the transmission schedule) is determined based on its assigned IP address.

Finally, the PC host connected to the router via an Intel I210 1 GigE interface, serving as the traffic-receiving endpoint. The host is equipped with an Intel AX200 802.11ax transceiver, which

is used to monitor and timestamp frames exchanged over the Wi-Fi network. Traffic sniffing is done using tools like *airmon-ng* and *Wireshark*. To access the content of transmitted frames, helpful for traffic characterization, Wireshark is configured with the Pre-Shared Key to decrypt AES-encrypted data sent by the STAs. The data are gathered by combining the information from the received application traffic and the sniffed frames.

Figure 3-12 Testbed components: 10 TWT-compatible stations (left side), Wi-Fi AP (right side), and Wireshark live capture (top).

The ESP boards can be programmed using the open-source Espressif IoT Development Framework (ESP-IDF), which enables firmware development and flashing. ESP-IDF also includes an application example for TWT, which can be used as base to develop a firmware capable of setting implicit TWT agreements. Specifically, the following parameters can be adjusted:

- TWT setup command
- Minimum wake duration
- Wake interval
- TWT offset
- Announced TWT
- Triggered TWT.

The above testbed will be used to show the benefits of the TWT mechanisms for the transfer of TS traffic in Wi-Fi, using off-the-shelf devices. Such results, under different transmissions scheduling policies, will be shown in D3.3.

3.4.2 Optimized Window Reservation for TSN Traffic over Wireless Links

This research presents a new approach aimed at reducing the amount of radio resources required to support multiple TSN flows over a wireless link. The objective is to minimize the frame duration needed to accommodate a given number of TSN flows while meeting delay guarantees (bounded delay and zero jitter). A shorter frame reduces the control cycle duration, which is crucial for certain remote-control applications. Conversely, for a fixed control cycle, the proposed design maximizes the number of supported TSN flows. The key idea is to design the frame with consideration for the variability in terminal connection bit rates caused by fast fading in wireless environments. The results included in this section were presented in the PIMRC'2024 conference (El Kaisi, Villares and Muñoz, 2024).

Problem Statement

We consider multiple stations accessing the same AP, following one of the coordination strategies supported by the latest IEEE 802.11 standards, such as the Target Wake Time (TWT) mechanism discussed in Section 3.4.1. Regardless of the selected coordination method, we assume that the AP gains control of the access channel and schedules the transmission of active uplink and downlink flows in distinct time intervals, thereby avoiding collisions and ensuring deterministic packet forwarding over the wireless link. The adopted time scheduler is designed to be compatible with the window-reservation standard 802.1Qbv (IEEE 802.1Qbv, 2016), providing an efficient way to implement this standard on wireless links with randomly varying data rates. The proposed radio frame is structured as presented in Figure 3-13.

Figure 3-13 Time-Division Duplexing (TDD) radio frame

It is assumed that the TSN flows are periodic with a common period T , which is multiple of the radio frame duration T_f . For simplicity, we consider that $T = T_f$. In this case, one transmission window of a convenient duration is periodically reserved in every frame. For compatibility with WiFi standards, all time intervals are multiple of one OFDM symbol. This minimum scheduling unit is hereinafter referred to as a time unit. The explanation will focus on the DL, although it is also applicable to the UL if the UL windows are extended $T_{p,UL}$ seconds to include L1 preambles and guard intervals.

Statistical design of windows

Zooming in on the DL, the detailed structure of every frame is given in Figure 3-14.

Figure 3-14 Detailed picture of the DL frame section and its k^{th} window

In every frame, a window of N_k time units are reserved for the k th flow. This window is opened at time $t_{k,start}$ and closed at time $t_{k,end}$. The time required to transmit a packet of B_k bits can vary from frame to frame due to the time-varying (random) transmission rate R_k . Accordingly, the value of N_k is decided so that the required transmission time $s_k = \text{floor}\left(\frac{B_k}{R_k}\right)$ rarely exceeds N_k . In particular, N_k is designed statistically so that

$$\Pr(s_k \geq N_k) \leq p_k$$

with p_k the accepted packet loss. Note that a packet is declared lost, and hence not transmitted, if it does not fit within its window. Because $R_k \in \{r_0, r_1, \dots, r_{max}\}$ is a discrete random variable, it follows that

$$N_k = \text{ceil}\left(\frac{B_k}{r_k^*}\right)$$

with r_k^* the faster Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) that allows to design the k th window with the agreed probability of loss p_k . Therefore, the minimum number of time units that are required to accommodate K DL flows in separated (orthogonal) windows is given by

$$T_{DL} \geq \sum_{k=1}^K N_k = \sum_{k=1}^K \text{ceil} \left(\frac{B_k}{r_k^*} \right)$$

The windows design can be done offline since it is purely statistical. During execution, at the beginning of every frame, the instantaneous rate R_1, \dots, R_K of all the flows is estimated. If $R_k < r_k^*$, the packet is lost with probability $p_k < \dot{p}_k$. If $R_k = r_k^*$, the packet occupies the whole window, whereas, if $R_k > r_k^*$, only the first $\text{ceil} \left(\frac{B_k}{R_k} \right)$ time units of the window are occupied, as indicated in Figure 3-14. The remaining $N_k - \text{ceil} \left(\frac{B_k}{R_k} \right)$ time units are, in principle, wasted, resulting in an important loss of efficiency. A solution is to allocate other non-TSN flows to these empty time units. We present hereinafter an alternative approach based on *overlapped windows* that compacts the transmission of TSN packets avoiding empty time units.

Overlapped windows design

We consider the design of windows that open before the previous ones get closed. In Figure 3-15, we show the structure of the window associated with the k th flow. The window is composed of two regions. The first region, Region A, goes from the opening of the window at $t_{k,start}$ until the closing of the previous window at $t_{k-1,end}$. The second region, Region B, is the portion of the window from $t_{k-1,end}$ to $t_{k,end}$. Although more than one window could get closed after $t_{k,start}$, to keep the explanation simple, we will assume that $t_{k-2,end} \leq t_{k,start}$.

Figure 3-15 Window structure with overlapping.

In Region A, flow $k-1$ has priority and can use as much time as required to complete its transmission, while flow k is only allowed to use the leftover time. This reduces the number of empty time units in window $k-1$ without altering the operation of this flow, which is unaware of the overlap. In Region B, the k th flow does not overlap with previous windows and thus can use the time in this region without restrictions. The following window $k+1$ will overlap with window k , but this overlap will not affect the scheduling of flow k .

The occupancy of time in region A by previous flows is characterized by a random variable s_k . The window length N_k is now selected according to this condition:

$$\Pr(s_k \geq N_k - M_k) \leq \check{p}_k$$

resulting in a window that is longer than in the non-overlapped case. This increase depends on the degree of overlapping, which is ultimately determined by $t_{k,start}$.

As $t_{k,start}$ decreases, Region A becomes larger, and Region B tends to decrease, reducing the overall frame length. Indeed, the frame duration is minimum when $t_{k,start} = t_{1,start}$ (for all k). We refer to this configuration as *full overlap* since each window overlaps completely with all the previous ones. With this setting, window lengths N_k increase with k , and the window associated with the last flow $k=K$ is as long as the whole frame. This makes this configuration generally not practical since it results in flows with very different delays, most of them being intolerably large. To keep the delays under acceptable values, we impose a second condition when designing the windows:

$$N_k \leq \check{d}_k$$

where \check{d}_k is the maximum tolerable delay for flow k . Note that \check{d}_k cannot be lower than N_k^{min} , which is the duration of the non-overlapped window ($M_k = 0$). The case $\check{d}_k = N_k^{min}$ is referred to as the *minimum delay* configuration.

The design of each window requires knowing the lengths and opening instants of previous windows. Thus, it is necessary to design windows recursively in ascending order as given by their indexation k . Note that the first flow does not have any previous windows and thus is designed as in the non-overlapped case, that is $N_1 = N_1^{min}$. In practice, the iterative procedure in Figure 3-16 is used to design the k th window with as much overlap as allowed by the design constraints:

```

1:  $t_{k,start} \leftarrow t_{k-1,end} - \check{d}_k$ 
2: if  $t_{k,start} < 0$  then
3:    $t_{k,start} \leftarrow 0$ 
4: end if
5:  $N_k \leftarrow \infty$ 
6: while  $N_k > \check{d}_k$  do
7:    $t_{k,start} \leftarrow t_{k,start} + 1$ 
8:    $F(x) \leftarrow CDF(s_k + M_k)$ 
9:    $N_k \leftarrow \min(x) : F(x) \geq 1 - \check{p}_k$ 
10: end while

```

Figure 3-16 Algorithm to compute the start and duration of windows.

In Figure 3-17, we provide a graphical example of the overlapped design. Overall, this design presents an intrinsic trade-off between delay and frame length, where the extremes are the *minimum delay* configuration ($d_k = N_k^{min}$), resulting in a long radio frame, and the *full overlap* configuration, yielding minimum frame length but large delays.

Figure 3-17 Overlapped windows example

At the beginning of every frame (using the DL preamble), the AP has to inform the stations when they will start receiving data from the active DL flows and what the burst duration s_k of each flow is. The first information is actually the delay M_k with respect to the start of the window. If the packet length is fixed, both M_k and s_k can be deduced from the MCS of the current flow and the previous ones. This information needs to be updated every time the propagation channel changes significantly, which happens every coherence time (about 10-30ms in industrial environments (Seijo et al, 2021)). Regarding the UL, the stations must also be informed about when they are expected to start transmitting (M_k) and for how long (s_k). This information must be included also in the DL preamble.

Simulations

A wireless access network founded on the standard 802.11ax (IEEE 802.11ax, 2021) is considered for evaluating the proposed windows design. The time unit is set to $T_{slot} = 13.6\mu s$, which corresponds to one OFDM symbol with an 800 ns guard interval. The transmission bandwidth is set to 20 MHz with 234 data subcarriers. The MCS is selected based on the *effective SNR*, a link quality indicator that is a function of the SNR of all the data subcarriers. From the MCS table in the standard, comprising 11 schemes, we select the highest MCS that guarantees a Block Error Rate (BLER) not higher than 10^{-4} for a Low Density Parity Check encoded block of 1458 bytes. A low BLER is adopted because retransmissions are not feasible for the studied delay-constrained system. The effective SNR is evaluated using the Received Bit Information Rate, a mutual information measure that was adopted by the 802.11ax task group for physical-layer abstraction (Anwar et al., 2019) (Matlab PHY, 2021).

We consider a random fading channel with an exponentially decaying power-delay profile and delay spread of 50ns (Seijo et. al, 2021). The received channel components are uncorrelated and Rayleigh-distributed. The coherence time is assumed to be much longer than the frame length. The average received SNR of all stations is set to 20 dB.

We consider identical flows that transmit packets of $B_k = B = 1500$ bytes every T seconds, with T adjusted to the frame duration $T_f = T_{p,DL} + T_{DL} + T_{UL} = \frac{2T_{DL}}{0.9}$, where it is assumed that $T_{DL} = T_{UL}$ (balanced DL and UL traffic) and $T_{p,DL} = 0.1T_f$ (typical 10% L1 overhead). Note that T_{DL} is the time required to multiplex in time K DL windows according to the proposed design. The window length is defined under a packet loss probability equal to $p_k = \dot{p} = 2 \cdot 10^{-3}$.

Figure 3-18 shows the frame length as a function of the number of flows for the non-overlapped design and the overlap design with different delay constraints $\dot{d}_k = \dot{d}$. The non-overlapped window duration $N_k^{min} = N^{min}$ is equal to 52 time units ($707.2\mu s$), which is the transmission time associated with MCS1 (Quadrature Phase-Shift Keying modulation and code rate 1/2). The delay constraints have been selected based on N^{min} and expressed as a factor N^{min} in Figure 3-18.

Figure 3-18 Control cycle (frame length) vs. number of flows

All configurations show a linear increase with the number of flows, although with different slopes. For constraints $\dot{d}_k = 2N^{min}$ and $\dot{d}_k = 1.5N^{min}$, their curves coincide with each other and barely differ from the *full overlap* case. This implies that we can minimize the frame length by

only increasing 50% the delay of flows. Another interesting conclusion is that the minimum delay constraint, $\hat{d}_k = N^{min}$, even though it results in a notable increase in frame length with respect to the *full overlap* case, still provides a much shorter frame than the non-overlapped windows design, all while constraining the delay to the same minimum value.

The throughput is the amount of information transmitted per unit of time, which equals:

$$TH = \frac{2K \cdot B}{T_f} = 0.9 \frac{K \cdot B}{T_{DL}}$$

Figure 3-19 shows the throughput of the same configurations simulated previously.

Figure 3-19 Throughput vs number of flows

The non-overlapped design shows a constant throughput along K , proportional to the transmission rate selected to design the length of the windows for a packet loss of $\hat{p} = 2 \cdot 10^{-3}$, which yields $R_k = r_k^* = 16.97$ Mbps. The overlapped windows design initially shows a rapid increase with K and converge asymptotically to a constant rate. Interestingly, the value that the full overlap curve tends to is the throughput that would result if the transmission time of every packet was equal to its average, i.e., $s_k = E\{s_k\}$. This upper bound is shown in Figure 3-19 as a dashed line. As a reference, this throughput is over 3 times larger than the non-overlapped one. However, the upper bound can only be (nearly) achieved by implementing *full overlap* with an unreasonable number of flows. Looking at a realistic number of flows, for instance $K=10$, if

a minimum delay is desired ($d_k = N^{min}$), the throughput gain with respect to the non-overlapped case is 82%. In cases with more delay tolerance (>50%), this gain could reach up to 127%.

3.4.3 Wi-Fi Dynamic DL/UL Splitter

As stated in the introduction of Section 3.4, the DL/UL splitter dynamically decides the allocation of time for UL and DL transmissions. Once the decision regarding the allocation of resources to UL and DL is made, the next scheduling levels, i.e., the UL and DL schedulers, operate independently. The DL scheduler coordinates the allocation of radio resources for different types of DL traffic, including DL Isochronous TSN traffic, DL Asynchronous TSN traffic, and DL best-effort traffic. A parallel approach is followed for the UL. In this subsection, new DL/UL splitters (Cabrera-Bean, Pan and Vidal, 2024) –both custom-designed and reinforcement learning-based– are presented and applied to a Wi-Fi link.

Problem Statement

The DL/UL splitter subsystem operates at the periodicity of a wireless frame. To ensure compatibility with Wi-Fi standards, frames with a 10 ms duration have been adopted in the simulations presented in this subsection, with each frame comprising 2500 time units. At the onset of each frame, depending on the state of the asynchronous TS traffic queues and possibly other factors, it decides the proportion of free time distribution between DL and UL. To do it, once the isochronous traffic has been allocated in the wireless frame (the occupied time in Figure 3-20), the non-occupied time units (N), are dynamically distributed between UL and DL.

Figure 3-20 Wireless Scheme

At the beginning of frame number t , an action A_t is selected from a set of potential actions, $A := a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{(N_a)}$ where $N_a = |A|$ is the size of the set of actions A and each action determines the UL/DL time proportion.

A FIFO queue is associated to each flow to keep incoming packets waiting to be transmitted through the wireless link. Depending on the wireless channel conditions, modelled through the coherence time and the instantaneous signal to interference plus noise ratio and also depending on the required BLER, an MCS is adopted for each flow, which determines the flow transmission rate. A range of algorithms is introduced. Each algorithm adopts the action taken in each frame based on all or some of the following pieces of information, measured at time starting frame number t .

- $q_{DL}(t-1, n), (q_{UL}(t-1, n))$: instantaneous aggregated content of the queues associated to the DL (UL) flows at the end of time unit n in previous frame $t-1$.
- $R_{DL}(t) (R_{UL}(t))$: transmission rate averaged over the users in the DL(UL) measured at the onset of the current frame.

- $T_{DL}(t)$ ($T_{UL}(t)$): time required to send all buffered DL (UL) traffic over the wireless channel.

Note that $R_{DL}(t)$, $R_{UL}(t)$, $T_{DL}(t)$, $T_{UL}(t)$ and are computed once the MCS for each flow at the frame time periodicity is determined. To keep the queueing delay of all aperiodic TS packets within moderate limits, it is crucial to maintain a balanced state between the UL flow queues and the DL ones. The average imbalance is measured at the frame periodicity, by introducing the variables $\mu_q(t)$, $\mu_r(t)$, and $\mu_T(t)$. These variables are updated at the end of the $(t - 1)$ -th frame, as:

$$\mu_q(t) = \frac{1}{N_T} \sum_{n=1}^{N_T} \frac{q_{DL}(t-1, n)}{q_{DL}(t-1, n) + q_{UL}(t-1, n)}$$

$$\mu_r(t) = \frac{R_{DL}(t)}{R_{DL}(t) + R_{UL}(t)}$$

$$\mu_T(t) = \frac{T_{DL}(t)}{T_{DL}(t) + T_{UL}(t)}$$

While average ratio $\mu_q(t)$ measures the imbalance between UL and DL queues, which is influenced by actions in previous frames and traffic arrival statistics, the ratio $\mu_r(t)$ depends solely on the conditions of the wireless channel of every use, instead the imbalance in transmission time, $\mu_T(t)$, depends on both, queue size and channel conditions.

For the sake of simplicity, a single flow is associated to each user. Regarding the queue management, queues are operated in FIFO mode and are managed using a circular buffer with a size of $N_b = 1000$ packets. Packets in the queue are considered lost if either their waiting time in queue exceed the maximum latency requirement (δ) for their traffic type or if a new packet arrives when the queue is full, in which case the packet at the front of the queue (the first position) is discarded. In neither of the two aforementioned circumstances is the packet transmitted.

At this point, the problem is stated as follows. At the start of each frame, a decision must be made regarding the allocation of free time between UL and DL. This decision should aim to keep the flow queues between UL and DL as balanced as possible, which objective is fulfilled by minimizing a target function specified below that aims for $\mu_q(t) = 0.5$. Additionally, our goal is to minimize the number of lost packets in queue, whether due to excessive waiting time or maximum queue occupancy.

Methodology

Five splitter algorithms are proposed: First a static splitter, second, two heuristic baseline algorithms, and third, two Reinforcement Learning (RL) based algorithms (Sutton and Barto, 2018).

- Static Splitter (SS): It allocates exactly half of the time to UL and the other half to DL and is included for the purpose of comparison.
- Heuristic Baseline Queue Size Proportional Splitter (QSPS): The free time allocated to UL (DL) is proportional to $\mu_q(t)$, so traffic excess can be accommodated with low outage. QSPS assigns to DL a number of time units, $N_{DL}(t)$ proportional to the percentage of the DL buffered traffic by using a quantified value of $\mu_q(t)$.

$$N_{DL}(t) = (i - 1) \text{round}(N/(N_a - 1)) \text{ if } i - 1 \leq N\mu_q(t) \leq i$$

- Heuristic Baseline Waiting Time Proportional Splitter (WTPS): Taking advantage of the average transmission bit rates knowledge, time is allocated proportionally to the average time required to empty the UL (DL) queue. Therefore, the percentage of time devoted to DL, at the start of frame t results:

$$N_{DL}(t) = (i - 1) \text{round}(N/(N_a - 1)) \text{ if } i - 1 \leq N\mu_T(t) \leq i$$

- Q-Learning (QL) Splitter: The QL approach is one of the most effective model free approaches to rapidly learn an optimal policy π^* by estimating the action-state value function $Q^*(s, a)$ iteratively, according to the Bellman equation-based iteration:

$$Q(S_t, A_t) = (1 - \alpha)Q(S_t, A_t) + \alpha \left(r_t + \gamma Q(S_{(t+1)}, A_{(t+1)}) \right)$$

where state $S_t = i$ if $i - 1 \leq N_s\mu_q(t) < i$ for $i = 1, \dots, N_s$, and N_s is the number of states, γ is the discount factor, and α is the learning rate. The reward function r_t is designed to maintain a balance between the aggregated queues while also penalising packet loss:

$$r_t = -|\mu_q(t) - 0.5| - L(t)$$

Where $L(t)$ is a counter of lost queueing packets during the past frame $t-1$. During training, the $Q(s, a)$ function is learnt over N_e episodes, with each episode consisting of N_f steps, with each step corresponding to one wireless frame. The RL agent follows the standard ϵ -greedy policy with time-decaying ϵ , starting with a high degree of exploration and gradually shifting towards more exploitation.

- Deep Q-Network (DQN) Splitter: In DQN a neural network (NN), $Q(s, a; \theta)$, plays the role of Q-table, providing the Q-value function for any state-action pair. During training, after frame t , the NN parameters θ_t are updated based on a training batch of size $L = 32$, resulting from a random sampling over a replay buffer that, at frame t , has a maximum of $H=10000$ experiences $(S_i, A_i, R_{i+1}, S_{i+1})$, for $i = t - H, \dots, t$, to break the temporal correlation of training samples. Beyond the experience buffer, a secondary NN, named target NN, is also introduced to generate a less fluctuating reference signal, which is updated periodically through the primary NN. The target NN, with same structure as the trained one and parameters θ' , is used during training to evaluate the Q-value function and minimize the Mean Square Error (MSE):

$$MSE(\theta_t) = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{i \in H_t} (R_{i+1} + \gamma \cdot \arg \arg Q(S_{i+1}, a', \theta'_t) - Q(S_i, A_i, \theta_t))^2$$

where H_t comprises the L indices of the batch experiences randomly drawn from the replay buffer at frame t . The DQN splitter, as the QL, follows an ϵ -greedy policy with same decaying ϵ and same reward function r_t . In contrast, unlike QL, in DQN the state has been modelled using a two-dimensional vector of continuous inputs.

$$S_t = [\mu_q(t) \mu_r(t)] \in R^2$$

Accordingly, the DQN architecture consists of an input layer (two entries as the state dimension), followed by two hidden layers with 64 and 32 neurons respectively, and an output layer with N_a neurons, each corresponding to a possible action.

Simulation Results

Generated traffic: DL packets originated at the AP and UL packets at user devices. All packets are of a fixed size of 720 bits. Packets from different flows enter a FIFO queue, since they cannot be sent instantly. Each aggregated queue (DL or UL) contains packets from N_{flow} flows. The variable N_{flow} is generated randomly in the range [1, 150] and is different between DL and UL. The time interval between two consecutive packets from the same flow (UL or DL) that enter the queue is modelled as Poisson (Mean inter-arrival time parameter is 5ms.). The channel status, distinct for each flow, determines the transmission rate using an appropriate Modulation Coding Scheme (MCS) that adapts to varying channel conditions ensuring a BLER below 10^{-4} . We have considered a Wi-Fi physical layer based on the 802.11a/g standard (non-HT format). In the simulations, channel status is generated randomly with a periodicity equal to the channel coherence time.

Training of RL algorithms: The learning phase for both, QL and DQN solutions, relies on interaction characterized by random initial exploration. Following hyperparameter optimization stages, training was conducted over $N_e = 800$ episodes, with each episode comprising $N_f = 900$ frames or steps. In each step, the RL agent takes an action that consists of planning a frame according to the information provided by the current state and receives feedback from the environment. Both, QL and DQN algorithms have been trained considering $N_s = 11$ states and $N_a = 11$ actions, with discount factor $\gamma = 0.9$, learning parameter $\alpha = 0.1$ (QL), 0.001 (DQN).

Figure 3-21 top left shows how the reward function in QL is affected by packet losses at the beginning of training. Per frame reward and averaged over a 50-frame window reward are shown. Once Q function is learnt, reward stabilizes at high values with no packet losses. Learnt QL table in terms of state-action and number of visits per state-action pair is included (bottom left). Regarding the learnt Q-function, it is observed that in states corresponding to more loaded UL queues, higher actions are chosen, which correspond to a greater allocation of time to the UL. The number of visits (bottom, middle) per state-action pair is also provided to validate the conditions under which the Q-table has been computed.

In Figure 3-21 top right, per frame reward and averaged reward over a 50-frame window are shown for the DQN algorithm. The DQN reward exhibits an increasing trend over the epochs, denoting that there are no lost packets after 40000 frames (500 episodes) while the average UL and DL queueing delay (bottom left), i.e., the mean waiting time in the queue for all packets that were successfully transmitted, decreases.

Figure 3-21 RL Training results: QL (left); DQN (right)

After training the RL-based methods, they are validated alongside the heuristic techniques to compare their performance. The five algorithms presented were executed over 100 episodes of 100 frames each one. In validation, RL-based algorithms choose the action following exclusively a greedy policy, always selecting the one that provides a higher Q-value, and Q-functions are frozen, that is, the Q-table in QL or network parameters in DQN are no longer updated.

In Table 3-3 the performance of algorithms for $\delta = 10$ frames is displayed, showing average reward, average, variance, confidence interval and 90% percentile of queueing delay and average packet loss when maximum queueing delay is 10 frames. The DQN algorithm performs the best overall, achieving a higher average reward and exhibiting superior delay properties. The confidence interval is narrow enough in all cases to conclude that the delay figures are precise and reliable. DQN shows significantly better variability and percentile than the rest of algorithms.

Table 3-3 Algorithms performance; $\delta = 10$ frames

Measures	SS	QSPS	WTPS	QL	DQN
Avg. reward	-0.1472	-0.2171	-0.2048	-0.1487	-0.1042
Avg. delay (ms)	2.6841	2.7186	2.7102	2.5778	2.2411
CI 95% Inf	2.6806	2.7155	2.7071	2.5746	2.2386
CI 95% Sup	2.6875	2.7219	2.7135	2.5811	2.2436
Var of delay	8.9061	7.772	7.8494	8.1114	4.8347
90% Percentile	5.1271	6.6671	6.6057	5.7855	4.8823
Avg. packet loss	3.42e-07	0	0	0	0

Similarly, Table 3-4 shows results of a scenario where a more restrictive maximum delay has been imposed. In it, SS achieves the highest average reward, but this is outweighed by its packet loss issue. On the other hand, when stringent latency requirements are imposed, WTPS also experiences occasional packet losses. Among the remaining algorithms, DQN exhibits superior properties by avoiding packet loss and achieving lower latency values alongside significant rewards.

Table 3-4 Algorithms performance; $\delta = 1$ frame

Measures	SS	QSPS	WTPS	QL	DQN
Avg. reward	-0.1671	-0.2101	-0.2468	-0.2155	-0.2021
Avg. delay (ms)	2.8488	2.9044	3.0513	2.8985	2.8263
CI 95% Inf	2.8456	2.9012	3.0476	2.8952	2.8231
CI 95% Sup	2.8521	2.9077	3.0551	2.9019	2.8296
Var of delay	8.7687	8.7758	11.6035	9.2331	8.7484
90% Percentile	5.9486	6.9311	7.1202	6.9632	6.6282
Avg. packet loss	6.28e-06	0	1.63e-04	0	0

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude that DQN consistently demonstrated superior performance in minimizing delay and packet loss, due to its lookahead capabilities, and that the use of channel information based on the transmission rate has improved performance. Furthermore, it has been generally observed that RL-based algorithms outperform heuristic algorithms, suggesting that the optimal dynamic time allocation strategy can be learnt through interaction with the environment.

3.4.4 Leverage multi-radio/MLO (Wi-Fi 7) towards seamless roaming

The objective of this activity is to achieve deterministic communication within a hybrid network that utilizes both Wi-Fi 7, featuring MLO, and Ethernet. To evaluate MLO for seamless mobility and enhance deterministic communication, an Artificial Intelligence (AI) model is trained to predict Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and classify the connection between the STA and the AP.

The entire project has been implemented and tested using the ns-3 simulation environment. The testbed comprises a hybrid network, as depicted in Figure 3-22, assuming an obstacle-free environment. It includes a mobile station, two fixed APs, a server, and an offboard controller. In this setup, the station serves as the source node, while the server is the destination. The station communicates over Wi-Fi 7 with MLO, utilizing three frequency bands, i.e., 2.4 GHz, 5 GHz, and 6 GHz, connecting to one AP at a time. Both APs communicate with the server via Ethernet. The decision on which AP the STA should connect to is based on the evaluation of KPIs, such as SNR and Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), for both APs. The controller performs the handover evaluation, determining the most suitable AP for the STA to connect to.

Figure 3-22 Network Configuration Implemented in the ns-3 Simulator.

The controller receives data from the STA and trains an NN to decide the optimal AP for the station. Data from the STA is collected at regular intervals (Δt). The features used to train the NN include the (x, y) coordinates of the STA, its velocities (v_x and v_y), and the fixed positions of both APs. The KPIs, considered as targets and acquired during simulations, are the RSSI and SNR values for both APs. To create the dataset, various trajectories, both linear and curvilinear, have been tested. Although no aggressors are currently considered, future plans include extending the dataset to account for STA aggressors sending UDP frames at different rates, allowing for network congestion evaluation through latency measurements for both APs.

The employed NN consists of a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network combined with a Binary Classification NN, as depicted in Figure 3-23.

Figure 3-23 Employed AI Model Combining LSTM and Binary Classification NN.

The advantage of this combination lies in the LSTM's ability to predict KPIs. Hence, by applying Binary Classification to these predictions, it is possible to determine in advance if the STA needs to perform a handover allowing also to know the time instant at which it must be completed.

The AI model is still under development. Currently, handover in ns-3 is managed based on the distance between the STA and each AP. At regular time intervals (Δt), the position of the STA is checked, and the distance to each AP is calculated. If the STA needs to connect to the first AP (AP1) and is already connected, the traffic flow between the STA and AP1 continues until the next position check. If the STA is connected to the second AP (AP2), the traffic flow between STA and AP2 is stopped at both the application and MAC levels, and UDP frames are generated from STA to AP1 at the application level. This process repeats at each position check. Similarly, if the STA needs to connect to AP2 and is already connected, UDP frames continue to be sent until the next position check. If the STA was previously connected to AP1, the running

application is stopped, and a traffic flow between STA and AP2 is restarted. A schematic representation of this procedure is shown in Figure 3-24.

Figure 3-24 Diagram Illustrating the Handover procedure based on distance STA-AP.

The next step involves adding traffic scheduling using the IEEE 802.1Qbv standard, part of the IEEE 802.1 TSN standards. This will be applied to all three wireless channels, allowing for the organization of scheduled windows to allocate time intervals for time-sensitive traffic (e.g., UDP frames) and handover operations. By predicting handover requirements in advance with the AI model and knowing the exact time it must occur, it is possible to schedule handovers during these scheduled time intervals without affecting the transmission and reception of time-sensitive traffic (Figure 3-25).

Figure 3-25 Application of IEEE 802.1Qbv on the wireless channel to schedule the handover without affecting the time-sensitive traffic flow

3.5 Enhancements to determinism on 3GPP networks

Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) has become a cornerstone for industrial communication, offering reliable, low-latency, and deterministic data transfer essential for modern automation and Industry 4.0 applications. Integrating TSN capabilities into 3GPP 5G networks, combined with advanced latency optimizations, extends these benefits across domains, seamlessly bridging traditional industrial Ethernet systems with 5G's advanced wireless infrastructure. This integration is transformative for cross-domain use cases requiring interoperability and strict performance guarantees.

We present latency enhancements to OAI 5G to meet these demands, including adaptive scheduling, traffic shaping, and resource allocation mechanisms designed to minimize latency and jitter for time-sensitive applications. We also explore TSN mechanisms implemented in commercial 3GPP networks, leveraging features like synchronous and asynchronous shaping, frame replication, and smart de-jittering to ensure reliable and deterministic communication.

Additionally, we introduce an XDP-based DetNet router, seamlessly integrated with 3GPP networks. This router supports advanced functionalities such as packet replication, elimination, and ordering, enabling robust performance for cross-domain applications. Together, these advancements establish a solid framework for industrial-grade communication across private and commercial 5G networks.

3.5.1 Enhancements on 3GPP latency

In this work, we extended OAI 5G to align with 3GPP's TSN specifications, introducing TSN capabilities to support reliable, low-latency communication crucial for time-sensitive applications in an open-source platform. These modifications adapt the platform to meet TSN's stringent requirements, establishing a solid foundation for further experimentation and development of TSN-enabled 5G networks.

Within the 3GPP domain, we deployed OAI as an open-source solution encompassing both RAN and 5G Core functionalities. The radio segment leverages a Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) to activate a physical cell on the n78 band with 20 MHz bandwidth, while core components are distributed across Docker containers. A commercial off-the-shelf terminal with a Linux-based host serves as the UE, enabling configuration of a network interface through the Linux kernel. To minimize interference during testing, both the USRP antennas

and the UE were placed in an isolated box with attenuators to emulate real-world signal propagation.

To address the lack of deterministic mechanisms in existing 3GPP open-source networks, we implemented several enhancements, including a traffic shaper, adaptive MCS selection, and a frame resource allocation scheme (Figure 3-26). The traffic shaper, built into the Linux queue discipline (qdisc), uses QoS Class Identifiers to manage non-deterministic traffic, shaping it according to the available link throughput. Additionally, the frame resource allocation specifically tailored for TSN minimizes jitter for time-sensitive traffic, ensuring reliable delivery for critical applications.

Figure 3-26 Enhancements on 3GPP domain

Adaptive Traffic Throttler: An adaptive throttling mechanism was developed to regulate incoming network traffic. This prioritizes TSN traffic and buffers non-priority traffic when throughput is constrained, guaranteeing adequate bandwidth for TSN traffic.

MCS Selection Adaptation: To avoid packet loss in TSN traffic, we modified the MCS selection, dynamically lowering the MCS to maintain TSN reliability and reduce latency and jitter by eliminating retransmissions over the wireless channel.

Frame Resource Allocation: A dedicated frame resource allocation strategy was introduced to handle TSN traffic, further reducing jitter and ensuring consistent transmission of periodic TSN data for critical applications.

In standard 3GPP systems, the default MCS algorithm maximizes throughput, selecting an MCS that maintains a BLER of up to 10%. To achieve bounded latency and eliminate Automatic Repeat reQuest retransmissions, we adapted the MCS to operate below the channel's capacity, achieving a BLER of 0% and enabling error-free over-the-air transmissions, albeit at the cost of reduced bandwidth.

We tested several MCS configurations to validate our approach while maintaining a deterministic 1 Mbps traffic load with varying levels of BE traffic. We examined three scenarios: with combined deterministic and BE traffic below, at, and above the radio link’s capacity, ensuring that BE traffic would not compromise deterministic traffic. Four MCS settings were tested—MCS 3, 9, 12, and 18—each using different MCSs. The system ran each test over five minutes with constant background BE traffic.

The results, illustrated in Figure 3-27 (right) show that under MCS 3, with a link capacity of 5 Mbps, BE traffic had no impact on the latency or packet loss of deterministic traffic, even at elevated BE levels (2, 4, and 10 Mbps). Figure 3-27 (left) depicts MCS performance under congestion, with MCS 3 consistently maintaining latency under 20 ms and achieving a BLER of 0. In contrast, MCS 9 and 12 exhibited increased latency due to less robust forward error correction, although with a BLER below 10^{-3} . MCS 18 resulted in higher latency, as retransmissions were triggered by the channel’s inability to sustain a low BLER.

These enhancements significantly improve both reliability and determinism in the 3GPP domain, effectively bounding deterministic traffic latency for time-sensitive applications, even in scenarios with substantial background traffic.

Figure 3-27: Performance for TSN Traffic for different MCS (left) and performance of BE (insight) + TSN traffic for MCS 3 with different channel usage

OIA scheduling algorithm allocates resources in the radio frame using Round Robin techniques, however if packets are released into the network periodically and synchronized with the radio frame, we can force them to always allocate the same subframe. Thus, we experience reduced jitter for all the TSN packets – see Figure 3-28.

By deploying these mechanisms within our 5G SA OAI network, we aim to provide a highly reliable and deterministic network environment, paving the way for innovative applications that demand stringent performance. In addition, depending on the latency and jitter requirements, our system chooses a configuration, scheduling TSN traffic within the frame in case it is necessary and achieving latencies from 7.3 to 9.8 ms in the best scenarios.

Figure 3-28 Latency distribution per packet for different traffic loads

3.5.2 TSN mechanisms on 3GPP networks

For 3GPP networks, we adhere to current standard architecture (3GPP TS 23.501, 2024) where the 5GS is presented as a TSN switch to others TSN network elements, by incorporating TSN-Translators in the UE and the Data Network side (DS-TT and NW-TT). This approach allows us to use existing, commercial 3GPP networks as they are and to create new TSN features on top of those networks.

Following the above approach, new TSN Translators, based on the XDP technology described above, are integrated with a commercial 5G network. New mechanisms and time-aware schedulers are deployed on top of the new TSN Translators, as described in the following subsections.

Although high performance is not in its objectives, currently the TSN Translators are able to process up to 2,70 Gbps, introducing a latency of 50 μ s. These numbers are more than enough to cover the Industrials use cases, where we have requirements of kbps in transmission and ms in latency (PREDICT-6G/D1.1, 2023).

Following, it is described the algorithms and mechanisms implemented and testing on a commercial 3GPP network.

3.5.2.1 Synchronous (adaptative) Packet Scheduler

This time-sensitive mechanism is based on the IEEE 802.1 Qbv (IEEE 802.1 Qbv, 2016), where the Time-Aware Shaper is defined. The main idea is to synchronize the use case traffic with time-windows to prioritize (or only allow) the critical traffic. On addition to the standard specification of the time-aware shaper, we develop an RL algorithm to adapt the time window to the external requirements.

We are using the synchronous scheduler in the ingress of the 5G system, where packet transmission is more predictable, and we can synchronize the 5G system and the producer of the traffic. We propose the use of synchronous scheduler to enhance the sharing of the radio resources, as described in Figure 3-29 by enabling the sharing of the resources not only in radio resources (e.g., spectrum) but also during the time.

In the Industrial Use case, we use a Non-Public Network deployment that shares radio and control plane with the public CSP (option 3 of 5G-ACIA (5G-ACIA NPN, 2019)). For guarantee the performance for NPN applications we create a radio network slice that reserve part of the radio resources for applications running on our NPN system, using Radio Resource Partitioning, as showed in Figure 3-29.

Figure 3-29 Radio Resource Partitioning with Time-Aware Shaper

On top of the Radio Resource Partitioning, we define a TAS with a window for TSN applications that can be synchronized with the TSN clients. As a novelty, we introduce a Reinforce Learning Agent that monitors the TSN traffic and is able to synchronize, by changing the TAS configuration, the TAS TSN window with the TSN packets. The Agent uses the following parameters:

- **State (Observations):** Per packet buffer time, packet buffering rate,
- **Actions:** TSN window size and relative position in a slot of 10 ms.
- **Reward:** A combination of buffer rate and time.

A demo of the Adaptive TAS can be found at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lpNtOzenat0&t=114s>

3.5.2.2 Asynchronous Traffic Shaper

Based on the specification 802.1Qcr, the Asynchronous Traffic Shaper is proposed for those scenarios where the endpoints are not deterministic. It provides three basic mechanisms:

- **Priority queue:** based on classification (e.g., PCP).
- **Traffic Shaping per class (stream filtering):** we define a maximum bit rate per class. This is implemented using a token bucket algorithm.
- **Urgent Base Scheduler (UBS):** Scheduler based on the Packet Delay Budget (PDB) of the packets.

This scheduler can be used in both ingress and egress of the 5GS. Obviously, in the ingress is more important the priority queue and the traffic shaping and for the egress, the key capability is UBS, which allows us to take into account the packet budget in the scheduling decisions.

3.5.2.3 Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability

The Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability (FRER) is a mechanism defined in IEEE 802.1CB for increasing the reliability of a network by duplicating frames. This mechanism is integrated in the TSN switch with the idea of replicating packets through different radio and user plane mechanisms, increasing with this the reliability of the 5GS.

In the implementation of the FRER mechanism we introduced an extension of the standard R-TAG, included in each of the frames, to include a partial timestamp in the frame. Please see the Figure 3-30:

0	1	2	3	4	5
Ether Type 0xF1 0XC1		Reserved		Sequence Number	

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Ether Type 0xF1 0XC1		Timestamp (32 bits)* <small>* 4 seconds in ns precision</small>				Sequence Number	

Figure 3-30 Standard (top) and extended (bottom) version of R-Tag

The timestamp is useful for other mechanisms, such as the Urgent-Base Scheduler, where is required to know the PDB of each packet. The extension is not standard and other Layer 2 elements will drop packets with this extension. But in our environment, next L2 switch is always the counterpart TSN-Translator, so it is safe to use it.

3.5.2.4 Smart De-jittering

As mentioned above, synchronous schedulers have not good performance at the egress of the 5GS, as the radio part introduce variability in the KPIs, specially in latency, so it is not possible to synchronize packets. For that reason, we use de-jittering mechanisms in the egress. Following, we describe the three option we tested:

- **Standard De-jittering (Hold-Forward):** Using the PDB, we define a target PDB that all packets shall fulfil.
- **Adaptative de-jitter** (Figure 3-31): The adaptative de-jitter is demonstrate in the video referenced in Section 3.5.2.1. The idea is to have an adaptative solution that, without having the timestamp in the packets, can de-jitter the TSN traffic. In this solution, the DRL agent knows that the TSN traffic is periodic and interacts with the adaptative de-jittering to tune the following parameters: default buffer time, time since last forwarding. Eventually, the agent can find the periodicity and to de-jitter the traffic.

Figure 3-31 Adaptive de-jitter

- **Smart De-jittering:** This is the evolution of adaptative de-jitter, where the DRL agent does not know the PDB of each packet and, in addition, knows nothing regarding the TSN traffic. The idea is to use the NPN DT to create synthetic traffic with the same response that the NPN system and to train a DRL agent with that. The DRL agent, based on the information that it can know (inter-packet arrival, last buffer time) is able to decide the de-jittering buffer time for each packet. The results were presented in the work *Smart De-jittering using Network Digital Twin* presented at 2024 IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom). As example, we included in Figure 3-32 an example of results using different methods of smart de-jittering on the Smart Factory Use Case.

Figure 3-32 Example of Smart de-jittering (Smart Factory, UL traffic)

4 Network and transport technology enhancement

4.1 Summary of updates

This deliverable builds upon the foundations set in (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023), and (PREDICT-6G/D2.2, 2023), to further enhance the PREDICT-6G framework’s networking and transport capabilities. While continuing to refine and expand upon the Linux-based, XDP/eBPF-driven TSN platform, this section also introduces significant updates to the concept of Data Unit Groups (DUGs). Although both efforts originate within the same project, they target distinct aspects of networking technology and are therefore presented in parallel.

Section 4.2 furthers the work begun in (PREDICT-6G/D2.2, 2023), on Data Unit Groups, which allows linking application-level data units to underlying transport mechanisms. This update introduces IPv6-based extension headers and TLVs to carry DUG metadata—such as sequence numbers, importance flags, and start/end markers—enabling more granular traffic engineering and prioritization. Critically, these enhancements are designed independently of the TSN/DetNet platform upgrades, offering a separate, standalone capability that can be applied or integrated into other network architectures as needed.

Building on the conceptual design and the initial TSN switch implementation, Section 4.3 transforms the baseline XDP/eBPF platform into a fully operational DetNet router. New functionalities, such as Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Functions (PREOF), MPLS tagging, and UDP/IP tunneling, have been integrated to achieve deterministic behaviors at scale. These additions empower the platform to serve as a flexible, programmable DetNet router that supports complex, latency-sensitive networking scenarios.

Both sets of enhancements have been validated to ensure that they do not adversely affect baseline performance. The TSN/DetNet router’s deterministic capabilities and the DUG metadata processing both maintain stable throughput and low latency under test conditions, confirming that these upgrades can coexist with high-performance networking requirements without degrading system stability or efficiency.

4.2 Data Unit Groups

XDP (eXpress Data Path) is a high-performance data path used to send and receive network packets at high rates by bypassing most of the operating system networking stack (eBPF, 2024).

In the context of packet processing, a packet entering the system through a network interface, XDP hook gets executed first. Here, the programs can filter, modify, or redirect packets based on various criteria, like packet content, metadata, or socket information (eBPF, 2024).

Along with XDP, a new address family in the Linux kernel called the AF_XDP is a raw socket optimized for high performance packet processing. As the socket can be used for both receiving and transmitting, it supports high performance network applications purely in user space (eBPF, 2024).

The following sections covers the updated implementation of Data Unit Group (DUG) concepts using XDP and AF_XDP and proposes a mechanism to convey the importance and related metadata of Data Unit Groups (DUGs) to DetNet routers presented in Section 3.2 in (PREDICT-6G/D2.2, 2023), allowing PREOF behaviour (D2.3) over DUG-aware DetNet routers (D2.2).

4.2.1 IPv6 Extension

This document proposes the introduction of DUG as an extension to the IPv6 header. To comply with this requirement and to follow the guidelines on how to design IPv6 header extensions (RFC6564, 2012), (RFC8200, 2017), i.e., using Type Length Values (TLVs), a new IPv6 TLV is defined. As the order of extension headers are fixed in IPv6, the DUG-related information is added to an appropriate IPv6 header option. The main purpose of the proposed DUG TLVs is for intermediate nodes to read the values and perform any DetNet queuing, shaping, scheduling, Ordering or even dropping over them. Thus, the "Hop-by-Hop" options header is identified as the most appropriate one, as intermediate nodes shall process the DUG-related information.

The IPv6 header option is illustrated in Figure 4-1 and is sequence in form of an unsigned integer number indicating the order of packets within a DUG. With each new packet, the sequence number is iterated by 1.

Figure 4-1 DUG metadata IPv6 option

The set of values describe the DUG as follows:

- DUG ID: an unsigned integer number identifying the DUG. The DUG ID of each new DUG is increased by 1 by the sender.
- Sequence: an unsigned integer number indicating the order of packets within a DUG, starting from 0 and increased by 1 for each packet in the DUG.
- D: This bit indicates the end of the DUG.
- I: These four bits indicate the importance of this packet against other packets in the same DUG. Lower values indicate a higher importance and allow to prioritize packets in different DUGs.
- Importance may be derived from the application type or the sensitivity of applications when not receiving a DUG in their application.
- C: A 1-bit field to indicate higher layer control plane packets. When reliable transport protocols are in use, e.g., TCP, or upper-layer control procedures take place, e.g., establishment of a Transport Layer Security session, there is no ADU exchanged. However, these control packets are equally important to the delivery of an ADU and depending on their functionality in the communication sometime even more important than the ADU itself. This bit allows to tag these packets.
- S: This 1-bit field indicates the start of a burst of packets within a DUG.
- E: This 1-bit field indicates the end of a burst of packets within a DUG.

Additional padding may be needed to make the hop-by-hop options header a multiple of 8 bytes long.

4.2.2 Router Behavior

A router can use DUG metadata to process packets belonging to the same traffic flow. For illustration, examples of such processing operations may include:

- For increased reliability, DetNet routers may use one or more DUG header options to apply frame replication or different queuing techniques. For instance, the C or I flag can indicate higher importance of a packet or set of packets within the DUG, e.g., the establishment of a Transport Layer Security session before the actual ADU is sent.
- In case of congestion where some packets need to be dropped, the importance can be used to determine which packets to drop. This can include a subset of the entire DUG, identified by their DUG ID, within a DetNet flow.
- Scheduling operations can use importance or other DUG metadata to determine which packet to send on which link. For example, the scheduler may forward packets on the same link used for other packets of the same DUG, to provide consistent treatment. In another example, packets of higher importance may be forwarded over higher quality links.

4.2.3 Implementation

The DUG-enabled router implementation utilizes Express Data Paths (XDP) hooks provided by the extended Berkeley Filters (eBPF) implementation in the Linux kernel (eBPF, 2024). The XDP hook implements the parsing of the IPv6 header and the DUG options as well as extended logging to feed packet treatment behaviors to the monitoring repository of a DT. Furthermore, the XDP hook implements a fixed cycle time to judge all arriving packets against and over which basic queuing and drop mechanisms can be applied.

Before testing the implementation, it was verified that the XDP hook has no negative impact on the actual networking performance of Linux.

As Figure 4-2 suggest, Packets are considered inside each DUG if they have the optional TLV field with optional type to identify the packets as DUGs. There is also a flow label to distinguish between packets that are part of the same flow. Once the packets are considered DUG, they are let through the kernel using the XDP_PASS action in the XDP hook and the packets are stored in the eBPF map.

Figure 4-2 Packet Processing Logic

The initial configuration of every eBPF program is the same, and they lack access to persistent memory storage within their program context. Instead, programs can access BPF maps

through auxiliary methods exposed by the kernel. BPF maps are referenced within eBPF code and defined upon loading an eBPF application. They are key/value stores. They can be shared between user space and kernel as described in Figure 4-3. Packets can be redirected from the kernel space to the user space for doing further operation. AF_XDP sockets allows the possibility for XDP program to redirect frames to a memory buffer in a user-space. Using the XDP_REDIRECT action in the XDP hook, the DUG packets are stored in the maps, directing it to the AF_XDP for them to access. The purpose behind this is mainly for Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Function (PREOF) of DUG to enable DetNet routing.

Figure 4-3 Overview of DUG-based DetNet Router Implementation Using eBPF

4.2.4 Validation

The validation of the eBPF-based DUG implementation is conducted in two steps: First, the implementation is validated against a non-eBPF network to ensure the software does not introduce any hit on the networking performance, such as packet delays, maximum throughput and packet loss. Second, the actual implemented PREOF functionalities inside the DUG-enabled DetNet router is then validated. This sub-section describes the first step.

To put the implementation under test, a network topology was created inside the lab, as illustrated in Figure 4-4. Four identical Dell Precision Tower 5810s with an Intel Xeon E5 1620 v3 CPU, clocked at 3.5GHz (4 physical cores with two hyperthreaded threads per core). All network interfaces for the illustrated network topology used the same Intel I210 gigabit ethernet NIC, offering a 1G connection. All nodes run an unmodified Ubuntu 24.04.1 LTS and each machine was put into the Performance mode in their BIOS.

Figure 4-4 Validation Testbed Topology To forward the packets to the receiver, the IP route which is enabled in sender and receiver are listed below:

Sender 1 & 2:

```
fdab:cef4:7d::/64 via fdab:bef3:7c::4 dev enp11s0 metric 1024 pref medium
fdab:cef4:7d::/64 via fdab:def2:7b::3 dev ens4 metric 1024 pref medium
```

Receiver:

```
fdab:bef3:7c::/64 via fdab:cef4:7d::5 dev enp0s25 metric 1024 pref medium
fdab:cef4:7d::/64 via fdab:cef4:7d::5 dev enp0s25 metric 1024 pref medium
fdab:def2:7b::/64 via fdab:cef4:7d::5 dev enp0s25 metric 1024 pref medium
```

To enable the forwarding, the `net.ipv6.conf.all.forwarding` is set to 1 in the file `/etc/sysctl.conf` in the forwarder node.

Each sender node, Sender 1 and Sender 2, have a single `IperfV6` instance running sending UDP traffic, a Scapy-based (Scapy, 2024) DUG traffic generator and an ARIA client (probing framework to determine link latencies and RTT and report it via a monitoring API to the AICP, described in Section 2.2.8 of (PREDICT-6G/D4.2, 2024)). Both `Iperf` and Scapy send their packets to the server and let the forwarder perform routing, whereby the link between the forwarder and the server becomes the bottleneck. Furthermore, an ARIA server is deployed on the forwarder, providing separate measurement data points for the link Sender 1<>Forwarder and Sender 2<>Forwarder. The Forwarder node also has an ARIA client deployed with an ARIA server on the

Server node, allowing the active measurement of link latency and RTT for the Forwarder<>Server link. For the validation of Step 1 (no performance impact by the eBPF-based DUG DetNet router), the chosen methodology is as follows: Scapy generates ~0.2 Mbps IPv6 traffic with the DUG header included and Iperf is configured using the bandwidth option -b to generate plain IPv6 traffic. On the Server, the received throughput by Iperf is recorded and used as the values on the x-axis in the two plots, provided in Figure 4-5 and Figure 4-6. Note, the x-axis values are UDP goodput values, i.e., the aggregated payload of Iperf UDP packets per second. The y-axis in Figure 4-5 provides the RTT on the Forwarder<>Server link in milli seconds (ARIA statistics), while the y-axis in Figure 4-6 provides the packet loss in % (Iperf statistics on Server). The measurements are then conducted with the eBPF implementation loaded and without, allowing a fair comparison between the two scenarios. Each data point in both figures is the aggregated value over seven independent 60s-long measurements, with each independent experiment conducted for 80s and the first and last 10s removed. From the measured RTT in Figure 4-5-, it can be concluded that both scenarios see an increase from 1.25ms for sub 100Mbps to 1.6ms for below the physical limit of the link of 940 Mbps (UDP goodput). XDP can help in achieving high performance and low latency (Paolo Abeni, 2018), further (Huanyi, 2022) highlighting that XDP can indeed bypass the TCP/IP kernel stack providing better performance, and to highlight this when looking closer to the graph, it can be observed that when the eBPF-based DUG DetNet router was loaded, the RTT increases at a slower pace with an increase of network load instead of having sudden spike like the RTT with no eBPF, which can be witnessed in Figure 4-5. Only when scratching the physical limit of the link (~940Mbps good put), the RTT is larger when the DUG DetNet was loaded.

Figure 4-5 Performance Validation of eBPF-Based DUG-Enabled DetNet Router - RTT

For the observed packet loss (Iperf statistics on server), Figure 4-6 provides the results and no difference between the two scenarios can be observed with a constant packet loss of 0% which only goes above 0% when scratching the physical limit of the Forwarder<>Server link.

Figure 4-6 Performance Validation of eBPF-Based DUG-Enabled DetNet Router - Packet Loss

When looking closer at the measured packet loss values (see Table 4-1), it can be even concluded that an eBPF-based router performs more reliable when moving closer to the physical limitation of the Ethernet link, without any observable packet loss.

Table 4-1 Packet Loss over Throughput Analysis for eBPF-based DUG-Enabled DetNet Routers

Aggregated Throughput [Mbps]	Packet Loss - no eBPF [%]	Packer Loss - eBPF [%]
918	0.00036	0
922	0.00039	0
928	0.0022	0
934	0.00272	0
940	0.66	0.65

4.3 DetNet router (implementation on XDP + eBPF platform)

Building on the achievements outlined in (PREDICT-6G/D2.2, 2023), where a fully operational TSN switch was developed leveraging XDP and eBPF, this deliverable introduces an advanced implementation of DetNet functionalities on top of the existing TSN switch infrastructure. The development draws directly from our prior work with DetNet implemented in P4, leveraging the insights and optimizations from that approach to build a robust, open-source, and more flexible DetNet implementation with XDP and eBPF at its core.

4.3.1 DetNet Functionalities over Software Defined TSN Switch Platform

Our initial TSN switch presented in (PREDICT-6G/D2.2, 2023), characterized by low-latency and high-reliability switching capabilities, now serves as the foundation for a DetNet-oriented network platform. This extension to a DetNet router builds upon the strengths of XDP and eBPF technologies, enabling high-performance, deterministic networking with the added flexibility to support complex DetNet configurations and integrations. This new DetNet router implementation seamlessly integrates functionalities essential to deterministic networking, including:

1. **Packet Replication, Elimination, and Ordering Function (PREOF)** – Ensuring that data packets follow strict ordering requirements, PREOF enhances deterministic traffic flow and provides the redundancy necessary for fault tolerance within the DetNet environment.
2. **MPLS Tagging and UDP/IP Tunneling** – For traffic identification and routing, our DetNet routers support MPLS tagging and encapsulation using UDP/IP tunneling, enabling efficient packet forwarding across DetNet and non-DetNet domains. This allows for streamlined traffic transitions, facilitating integration with broader network domains.
3. **Configurable Network Roles** – Our DetNet routers are designed to serve multiple roles depending on network architecture requirements:
 - **Encapsulators** for managing ingress traffic from non-DetNet to DetNet domains, adding the necessary DetNet headers and processing,
 - **Decapsulators** for egress traffic, transitioning from DetNet to non-DetNet domains,
 - **Forwarders** for standard deterministic packet handling within DetNet domains, and

- **Forwarder-Order-Replication-Elimination** nodes to fully leverage PREOF, ensuring compliance with strict packet delivery and sequencing standards.

Through these configurations, our DetNet routers are operational and capable of seamless integration within a broader TSN-oriented network infrastructure, creating a versatile, scalable, and reliable platform for deterministic networking. This level of integration positions the DetNet routers as critical components in constructing the PREDICT-6G data plane, as outlined in Section 5.4. By implementing these functionalities within the open-source, programmable environment of XDP and eBPF, we not only achieve greater flexibility but also provide a foundation for ongoing enhancements in TSN and DetNet network design within the PREDICT-6G framework.

4.3.2 Experimental Setup

To assess the performance of the implemented DetNet functionalities, we carried out latency measurements across key operations: encapsulation, forwarding, and decapsulation. These were evaluated both individually and in a complete end-to-end deployment that involved three interconnected DetNet routers. This testing setup allows for a deeper understanding of the latency characteristics and the cumulative impact of the DetNet data plane.

Figure 4-7 Measurements scenarios

Bidirectional traffic was generated between the User and the TSN Application, with a total load of 80 Mbps (40 Mbps in each direction). This was achieved by transmitting 1 kB packets every 25 ms, creating a realistic scenario for deterministic traffic handling. As illustrated in the measurement topology (Figure 4-7), the DetNet data plane consisted of three routers

configured to perform encapsulation (Router 1), forwarding (Router 2), and decapsulation (Router 3). This setup closely emulates a practical deployment scenario for a DetNet-based network.

4.3.3 Results

The latency results are presented in the accompanying CDF graph, which captures the following key observations:

1. **Individual Functionalities:**
 - a. Encapsulation, forwarding, and decapsulation were measured independently, revealing distinct latency distributions for each operation.
 - b. Encapsulation and decapsulation exhibit relatively similar latency profiles, while forwarding introduces slightly more delay due to increased headers processing.
2. **End-to-End Deployment:**
 - a. The cumulative latency of the complete DetNet deployment (encapsulation, forwarding, and decapsulation) is captured in the end-to-end CDF curve and shown in Figure 4-8 demonstrate that even with the added complexity of multiple operations, the platform maintains a predictable and deterministic latency profile.
 - b. Packets experience low latency, with minimal variability, validating the implementation's suitability for deterministic networking applications.
3. **Deterministic Performance:**
 - a. Across all scenarios, the CDF curves highlight the system's ability to achieve deterministic latency bounds, ensuring that packets are processed and delivered predictably within defined thresholds.

Figure 4-8 Latency distributions for each DetNet function

The source code for the implementation is available in the Predict6G GitLab repository and can be accessed at [Predict6G GitLab - P6-TSN-XDP-Switch](#).

5 Data plane architecture and cross-domain integration

5.1 Summary of updates

On the impact and requirements of deterministic service on end devices, (Section 4.7.1 in (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023)) already provided an analysis of basic requirements and considerations with regards to the internal implementation and architecture of end devices. The conclusion was that the end device needs to be able to control the packet delivery mechanisms (including memory transfers, schedulers, resource allocations, interrupts, etc.) between the inception of a packet (in a user space application) and the transmission of the

packet from the NIC. Section 5.2 in this deliverable provides a wider perspective of the end device's relation to the PREDICT-6G system, elaborating on potential interworking principles.

On the target deployment assumptions and multi-domain considerations, Section 3.3 and Section 5.2.2.2 of (PREDICT-6G/D1.2, 2023) already reported on the applicability of PREDICT-6G to both technology and administrative management domains. In this deliverable, Section 5.3 elaborates on different deployment assumptions considering a combination of technical and administrative domains.

On the DetNet based cross-domain integration of 5G, Wi-Fi and TSN, Section 4.4, 4.5 and 4.8 in (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023) provided only early considerations on challenges and potential approaches. In this deliverable, Section 5.4 reports on a successful integration of real TSN switches (by Telefónica), 3GPP (Ericsson), Wi-Fi (Intel) using DetNet as the End-to-End (E2E) integration layer.

On the non-deterministic devices and networks, Section 4.7 of (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023) provided initial considerations related to the impact of end devices on deterministic services. Section 5.3.5 of (PREDICT-6G/D1.2, 2023) reported the need to extend and instrument non-deterministic user planes with extended functionalities to compensate for the lack of native deterministic capabilities. In this deliverable, Section 5.5 provides a detailed methodology and apparatus to realize such extension. The provided solution is also implemented in the Nokia Lab and will be demonstrated in PREDICT-6G.

Finally, Section 5.6 provides an overview on the standardization activities related to WP2 work.

5.2 Impact and requirements of deterministic services on end devices

The main scope of PREDICT-6G is to enable deterministic communication between end devices through a set of heterogeneous network technologies and domains. The involvement of the end device in this communication may be analyzed from two views: from the control/management plane, and from the data-plane. While this deliverable focuses on the data-plane, for the sake of coherence, it briefly discusses the end device's interactions with the control/management plane as well, before focusing on the data-plane aspects.

First, as the general approach adopted in PREDICT-6G from the beginning (e.g., see Section 9 of (PREDICT-6G/D1.1, 2023)), the end device (or and end user owning the end device) may be involved in initiating a deterministic service through the AICP of PREDICT-6G. This interaction is open for any entity that wishes to trigger the establishment of deterministic services, regardless of whether the entity is purely an operational/administrative entity or also an actor in the deterministic communication itself. This interaction has no specific impact on the end

device apart from consuming the PREDICT-6G service ingestion API, but it's not tied to any data-plane capability, it is purely part of the control/management plane and therefore this interaction is not performed in the MDP.

Second, the integration of the end-device with the PREDICT-6G data-plane (MDP) is discussed, considering three alternatives that differ in the level of support for deterministic technology at the end device.

1. The ideal case is when the end device supports a deterministic technology, such as TSN and DetNet. This could be considered the future state of technology especially when it comes to new devices and deployments that are by design supporting use cases that require stringent end-to-end determinism (rather than being an after-thought on legacy devices). In this case, from data-plane protocol and procedure point of view, the PREDICT-6G MDP would reach into the end device itself. The AICP of the PREDICT-6G (especially considering the technology domain level abstractions provided by the AICP Management Services / OpenAPIs) would extend also to the end device similarly to any other intermediate device that is part of the technology domain.
2. Regardless of whether the first alternative above is realized, the end device's internal operations may have impact on its ability to truly participate in a deterministic service. The problem is that irrespective of functional and syntactic conformance to deterministic data-plane (supporting a standard DetNet encapsulation, timestamping, etc.), the internal packet delivery from application to NIC should conform also to the non-functional performance requirements of a deterministic data-plane. To this end, a "DetNet Socket" concept could be investigated, where the DetNet Socket represents the packet's lifecycle within the end device, and a DetNet Socket implementation is responsible to ensure that the packet's delivery from the application's buffer to the NIC supports the deterministic QoS targets that are defined for the deterministic data flow. Outside of the end device, the deterministic network services oversee ensuring deterministic packet delivery. Note that the DetNet Socket would be on top of a standard deterministic network stack, such as DetNet/TSN, therefore the DetNet Socket would not need to re-implement any of the deterministic mechanisms (such as PREOF/PAREO) as those would be provided by the DetNet/TSN layers. However, the DetNet Socket ensures that the device internal (e.g., userspace, kernelspace, interrupt, data/memory transfer, clocking, etc.) mechanisms are configured and necessary resources are granted to the deterministic packet flow so that the end device internals are not disrupting the delivery of packets before they are transferred to the underlying deterministic network technology. The DetNet Socket also has the scope to transfer application payloads to the underlying transport protocol stack, that is, add the relevant packet encapsulation and provision the header fields according to the

protocol's specification. For example, in case IETF/DetNet is used as the end-to-end protocol within the network, the IETF/DetNet encapsulation itself is sufficient to carry all relevant in-band information and thus no extra encapsulation needs to be added by the DetNet Socket.

3. It is possible that the end device does not support any deterministic network technology (e.g., legacy devices). In this case, the end device is not part of the PREDICT-6G MDP and its user plane capabilities are not managed by PREDICT-6G's AICP. Still, the end device may act as a consumer of the PREDICT-6G AICP for service ingestion, as discussed above, and could benefit from adopting over-the-top techniques that aim to improve the deterministic outcomes of serving data flows over a non-deterministic technology (see Section 5.5 in this deliverable).

In addition to the end device's involvement in the deterministic data-plane, there is an additional aspect of time synchronization in which the end device may also be involved. The intermediate network devices within PREDICT-6G MDP should be time synched to support coordinated actions required to serve time sensitive traffic. If the end device supports a deterministic technology and thus it's part of the PREDICT-6G MDP, the end device is time synchronized by the MDP technology itself (and using the PREDICT-6G TimeSync OpenAPI [Section 6.2]). However, if the end device is not supporting any deterministic technology, it may still obtain (or be provisioned) the same time synchronization as the MDP network devices. Maintaining time synchronization in the end device has two major benefits.

First, truly end-to-end measurements such as E2E delay or jitter require that the end devices (communication endpoints) are time synchronized. Such time sync is required to evaluate the PREDICT-6G system through the KPIs defined in Section 3 of (PREDICT-6G/D1.1, 2023). Further, channeling these measurements into the PREDICT-6G operation (e.g., through the Measurement Collection Managed Service (MS) Section 8.3 of (PREDICT-6G/D1.2, 2023)) enables the assurance of deterministic services based on real-time accurate insight to the E2E QoS of the deterministic flows.

Strictly, maintaining time sync among the end devices themselves (independently from the time sync of the MDP) would be sufficient to enable E2E measurements, but sharing the time sync between end devices and network devices has a further benefit of producing E2E measurements, logs and events comparable and time-aligned with measurements taken at intermediate network devices. This enables to build a coherent, causality-correct view of the PREDICT-6G system that covers also the end devices and enables to create and maintain accurate Network Digital Twins for the entire deployment.

5.3 Target deployment assumptions and multi-domain considerations

The PREDICT-6G reference architecture scales to multiple administrative domains and multiple technology domains, including their combination. Domains are expected to be stable/static, that is, not changing during the lifetime of the PREDICT-6G E2E deterministic sessions. The PREDICT-6G reference architecture separates the concerns of domain level service management and E2E service management into two layers on the management plane (AICP). This means that even if the PREDICT-6G system is instantiated to a deployment with a single administrative domain and a single network (with a given technology), the logical architecture differentiates the E2E and domain level management scopes. Note, however, that in any functional implementation the two domains may be implemented by the same management function(s). This is illustrated in Figure 5-1.

Figure 5-1 Single domain (both administrative and technical) PREDICT-6G deployment.

In a single administrative domain but with multiple networks of the same technology, the same domain level PREDICT-6G Management Services can be used to manage the domain level services within the boundaries of each network. This is due to the same interfaces (T1 API) exposed by each network and therefore it could be managed by separate instances of the same PREDICT-6G domain level Management Services (each dedicated to one of the networks), or by the same domain level Management Service instances given that their implementation can handle multiple domains (i.e., they can internally separate responsibilities towards more than one domain given that they provide the same technology). This is illustrated in Figure 5-2.

Figure 5-2 Single administrative domain, multiple technology domains (with the same technology).

Still remaining in a single administrative domain, multiple technology domains may be handled with different types of PREDICT-6G domain level Management Services, as shown in Figure 5-3.

Figure 5-3 Single administrative domain, multiple technology domains (with different technologies).

In case of multiple administrative domains, their scope may be split both horizontally (across different networks, providing the same or different technologies) and vertically (in the domain/E2E management concerns). A horizontal split requires the MDP inter-domain coordination is exercised across multiple administrative domains, as reported in Section 5.3.3 of (PREDICT-6G/D1.2, 2023). This practically means that the configurations to be provisioned at different administrative domains should be aligned to achieve a harmonized cross-domain impact on the data-plane. Achieving such coordination across administrative domains is outside of the scope of PREDICT-6G.

In one case, a primary administrative domain handles all vertical management scopes (domain and E2E level) but one of the networks (on the technical operation level) is provided by another administrative domain (Figure 5-4).

Figure 5-4 Multiple administrative domains, with asymmetric roles in the vertical management split (same technology per domain).

A similar case is when the two networks provide different technologies (Figure 5-5). In principle, there is no difference for the A2 administrative domain, whereas the A1 administrative domain must apply different types of domain level Management Services.

Figure 5-5 Multiple administrative domains, with asymmetric roles in the vertical management split (different technologies per domain).

Figure 5-6 Different administrative domains per network segment.

The vertical scope of the second administrative domain may be increased to also include the domain level deterministic service management. Regardless of whether the network

technology of the A1 and A2 scope are the same or different, the relation between the A1 and A2 are on the E2E integration. This is illustrated in Figure 5-6.

Finally, the administrative domain separation may also extend to moving the E2E scope under separate administration, as shown in Figure 5-7.

Figure 5-7 Separate administrative domain for pure E2E deterministic service management scope.

5.4 DetNet based cross-domain integration of 5G, Wi-Fi and TSN

Following the work presented in (PREDICT-6G/D2.2, 2023), this section details the evolution of the multi-domain use case, which involves a robot dog which is remotely controlled by an operator with multi-domain connectivity to the robot location. Comparing with what we

reported in (PREDICT-6G/D2.2, 2023), we enhanced the use case by incorporating gesture-based control and a DT of the robot within an industrial setting. Furthermore, we included all the updates on L2 enhancements proposed in the previous deliverable in Section 3 and created a new Section 4 with the enhancements on L3.

Regarding the architecture, it has been modified to create a more streamlined and efficient structure, fully supporting TSN capabilities across all three key domains—Wi-Fi, 3GPP, and Ethernet. This ensures end-to-end determinism and low-latency performance for the gesture-controlled robot dog. The new configuration begins with the operator, connected through a Wi-Fi TSN domain. From there, data is routed into an Ethernet TSN domain equipped with TSN switches, maintaining precise timing and synchronization throughout. The next phase is a 3GPP TSN domain provided entirely by Ericsson, which we chose to replace the OAI. While OAI remains an excellent tool for academic and research applications, this shift allows us to better showcase PREDICT-6G architecture’s end-to-end use case capabilities. Ericsson’s domain provides a more stable, reliable 3GPP TSN framework, which is crucial to realizing the practical, real-world integration of PREDICT-6G’s architecture.

In addition, the Telefónica switches, now incorporated into the Ericsson domain, provide TSN capabilities in the backhaul of the 3GPP network, between the core network’s UPF and the gNB, ensuring deterministic communication within the core-to-gNB link. This approach unifies Wi-Fi, Ethernet, and 3GPP under TSN principles in a fully integrated setup.

This revised architecture not only enables seamless end-to-end TSN support but also enhances network resilience and flexibility. For a visual representation of this updated setup, refer to Figure 5-8, which illustrates the communication flow through each domain and highlights the critical TSN transitions between Wi-Fi, Ethernet, and 3GPP domains.

Figure 5-8 Multi-domain Use Case architecture

This section also addresses the cross-domain integration that enables seamless communication across different technological domains. To integrate these domains and align with the PREDICT-6G architecture, we utilize DetNet routers as the foundational link between distinct technologies. Specifically, we employ our DetNet router, developed with XDP and eBPF, as the core element in bridging these domains. Further details on the design and functionality of this DetNet router are elaborated in Section 4.3.

Using these DetNet routers, we establish a DetNet-based data plane that supports end-to-end communication across varied domains, maintaining deterministic, low-latency connectivity. In Figure 5-9, we present the encapsulation process facilitated by these routers. The DetNet routers perform a range of essential DetNet functionalities, including tunnelling (via IP and UDP/IP), MPLS label tagging, and PREOF operations. Figure 5-9 illustrates how, within each domain, encapsulation and decapsulation occur, showcasing how tunnels are managed and adapted as data transitions between domains.

Figure 5-9 Multi-domain DetNet based data plane

Finally, our ongoing work focuses on achieving seamless integration across all technological domains depicted in the Figure 5-8 to establish end-to-end deterministic communication. As a next step, we aim to incorporate PREDICT-6G AICP that will manage the configuration of each technological domain and the DetNet routers to ensure a fully coordinated, deterministic network environment.

5.5 Non-deterministic devices and networks

The vision of PREDICT-6G is to have E2E deterministic services by leveraging L2/L3 deterministic capabilities of (potentially different) network technologies and enable the seamless composition of E2E deterministic services from any number of intermediate domain-level deterministic services. However, the current state of the art is that the standards for deterministic L2/L3 technologies such as TSN (IEEE 802.1 TSN Task Group, 2019) and DetNet (RFC8655, 2019) are much more developed than their adoption in practical deployments. Yet

the need to start deploying E2E deterministic services already exists, provided by the use cases (PREDICT-6G/D1.1, 2023). Reusing existing install base of non-deterministic enabled network devices is therefore a necessity on the path of transitioning to an E2E deterministic-enabled stack. This section reports the methodology and innovation within PREDICT-6G to enable the composition of non-deterministic network technologies into and E2E deterministic service. Non-deterministic networks here mean any technology that has no built-in support for handling deterministic flows such as time sensitive schedulers, de-jittering or PAREO capabilities. Even technologies for which such capabilities may exist in the standard, but are not implemented in a particular deployment, are considered in practice non-deterministic; such as a 3GPP network with no TSN support included.

Note that the level of determinism achieved by the reported means is not claimed to be on the same level as with network devices engineered with deterministic HW/SW support; however, depending on the service demand and KPI targets formulated for a specific use case, it may already enable to start using deterministic services without having to invest in extra equipment.

The key concept of improving the level of determinism in existing (legacy, non-deterministic) networks is to (1) provide real-time flow level insight to the service level and performance of packet delivery; (2) obtain the demand of each flow in terms of resources, time sensitivity and resiliency; (3) implement adaptive self-calibrating mechanisms that are capable of dynamically enforcing the separation of flows and allocation of resources per each flow according to their demand. Additionally, (1)-(3) should be agnostic to the underlying technology (except for basic principles such as using IP) and therefore be applicable to different networks including 3GPP (non-deterministic), Wi-Fi (again with no-deterministic features), IP, etc.

The concept is realized through defining a unified but configurable and adaptive entity referred to as the MDP Agent. The MDP Agent is a software module that is inserted into the data-plane at multiple locations and its role is to provide the (1)-(3) capabilities on behalf of the original data-plane that is natively incapable of them.

Figure 5-10 provides an example of deploying MDP Agents at various locations in a multi-technology multi-domain network, consisting of 5G, Wi-Fi and IP technologies (variants that have no underlying TSN integration or other technology specific deterministic enablers such as Wi-Fi TWT). The locations of the MDP Agents are selected to enable impact at any potential bottleneck and separate the E2E into segments where localized measurements and packet delivery mechanisms are governed by the MDP Agents. The setup enables to deliver different types of E2E deterministic services, including multi-domain multi-path, single domain single path, and multi-domain single path variants, depending on the use case and end devices.

Figure 5-10 Exemplary illustration of MDP Agent deployment in a multi-technology multi-domain network.

Note that the MDP Agent may be installed also on or next to end devices and thereby extending the impact of improved determinism truly in the end-to-end, up to the end devices. In virtualized environments, the MDP Agent may be running as a containerized (or VM based) software module hosted by the same compute node on which the end application is running, inserted in the virtual packet flow across containers/VMs, acting on an in-memory virtual link between the application and the MDP Agent. Although the virtual packet flow between the application and MDP Agent will not be managed in a deterministic manner, it can practically be regarded as having much higher capacity and throughput than what would introduce significant delays or jitters into the E2E communication. In bare-metal deployments, the MDP Agent may be running on the same host as the end application, as a different operating system process and having access to the packet flow between the application and the NIC, effectively playing the role of a “DetNet socket”. In case the MDP Agent is pinned to dedicated CPU resources that are receiving no interrupts, the MDP Agent could be an approximation of what a DetNet Socket could deliver in terms of transparently (but deterministically) bridging the application with the HW NIC, with the added benefit of allowing for the continued use of UDP (Datagram) sockets (and thus requiring no change in the application itself).

A network domain whose determinism is improved via the deployment of MDP Agents is considered a technology domain in PREDICT-6G. Accordingly, MDP Agents expose OpenAPIs to enable control and management through the domain level PREDICT-6G AICP Management

Services. As MDP Agents form a collaborative probe/action overlay that takes over the monitoring and service enablement responsibilities of the underlying network (at least the deterministic extent of it), the MDP Agents are the ones that collect and expose information (such as topology, resources and capabilities), provide the measurements of relevant KPIs (measurement collection), and deliver data-plane actions to enforce deterministic packet scheduling principles (service automation and resource configuration). As part of the service automation capability, the MDP Agents also receive the definition of deterministic services (as reported in Section 5.4.2 of (PREDICT-6G/D1.2, 2023)) such as the Traffic Flow Template of the deterministic flows to enable flow separation, and the QoS characteristics of the flows to enable the activation of the right scheduling, resource configuration and packet treatment mechanisms.

The MDP Agent supports a set of functionalities that is selectively activated depending on the deployment/location of the specific MDP Agent in the E2E path. The functional architecture and interfaces of the MDP Agent are shown in Figure 5-11 and defined as follows:

F1: Time Sync. All MDP Agents are time synchronized to create a distributed but time-aligned fabric of data-plane measurements and actions.

F2: Measurement actions. All MDP Agents perform a data-plane encapsulation/decapsulation (alternatives are discussed later) to enable in-band signaling of measurement beacons (such as flow identifiers, timestamps, sequence numbers) and computed measurement results that are relevant to downstream MDP Agents (such as the forwarding delay of the packet accumulated so far). MDP Agents perform actions on the packets to perform individual measurements, as well as in collaboration with other MDP Agents with which they share the same E2E path. Individual measurement actions include, e.g., flow detection and classification, timestamping, throughput and jitter measurement. Collaborative measurements include measuring one-way delays between segments defined by neighbouring MDP Agents, which require the exchange of information in the packet encapsulation. The measurements and the mechanism to obtain them are discussed later in this section.

F3: Scheduling and traffic shaping. MDP Agents may dynamically instantiate per-flow buffers to separate traffic that belongs to different deterministic services (and thus have different QoS characteristics), as well as to separate deterministic traffic from non-deterministic one (such as best effort traffic). Scheduling is most effective at deployment locations preceding a natural bottleneck in the E2E path, such as (usually) a radio interface. Therefore, this functionality does not need to be activated in all MDP Agents but only in those that precede (in packet forwarding direction) a bottleneck in the system. Of course, in case bottlenecks are not static, the functionality can be dynamically shifted (turned on) in other MDP Agents as well.

F4: De-jittering. MDP Agents may perform de-jittering by slightly delaying packets on their delivery to even out delay variation in subsequent packets or data bursts. This is mostly effective at the last MDP Agent in the E2E path. The de-jittering impact is minimized by adaptively self-calibrating the amount of extra delay to the minimum that meets the delay requirement defined in the deterministic flow’s QoS characteristics, based on a rolling statistical distribution of the measured E2E delay.

F5: Packet replication and elimination. MDP Agents may perform the equivalent of PAREO to take advantage of the lowest delay offered by a set of multiple paths. Additionally, multiple disjoint paths enable to improve resiliency of the E2E service by protecting against failures or the onset of transient congestion along a subset of the involved paths. Such functionality is needed only for those deterministic flows that require high E2E reliability (higher than what a single path can deliver).

* Based on own measurements, configuration, flow and service QoS requirement awareness

Figure 5-11 Internal functional architecture and interfaces of the MDP Agent.

The concept of collaborative measurements is illustrated in Figure 5-12 with an example of four MDP Agents deployed along a path at different locations. Each pair of neighboring MDP

Agents defines a segment (A, B, C) to which they can provide localized (segment specific) measurements, such as the forwarding delay of a packet transmitted along the path (segment by segment), or detecting a loss of a packet localized to one of the segments. This collaboration between adjacent MDP Agents is enabled by inserting or updating specific information elements in the data-plane encapsulation that each MDP Agent maintains. An additional capability of the MDP Agents is to also include cumulative measurements into the data-plane encapsulation; most prominently, the cumulative forwarding delay of the packet (technically, the time since the packet was timestamped at the first MDP Agent in the E2E path). This information is maintained at each MDP Agent to provide a real-time in-band indication of each packet's delay, carried by the packet itself. Combined with the knowledge of the QoS characteristics including the E2E delay target of the deterministic flow to which the packet belongs, the MDP Agent with activated time sensitive scheduling functionality in front of a network bottleneck can explicitly take this into account when scheduling packets (or performing de-jittering) to fit each packet into the envelope of expected traffic characteristic. Distributing this per-packet real-time information via off-band control plane across MDP Agents would not be feasible as the off-band traffic may get off-sync from the actual data-plane traffic (not to mention the extra overhead); whereas working with averages and aggregates would make MDP Agents lag behind the current real-time data-plane state and have no packet level granularity either. This packet level in-band signaling is maintained across technology and administrative domain borders, enabling consistent E2E deterministic QoS without relying on each domain's internal (lacking) deterministic capabilities.

Figure 5-12 Collaborative measurements between pairs of neighbouring MDP Agents.

Next, the details of the logical MDP Agent functionalities are discussed. Figure 5-13 shows the common functionality of flow classification and data-plane encapsulation at each MDP Agent according to their collaboration discussed in the context of Figure 5-12. The last MDP Agent in each path of course performs data-plane decapsulation after reading and utilizing the information from the packet.

* Note: shows only the elements relevant in the MDP Agent's action's context

Figure 5-13 Flow classification and data-plane encapsulation.

The delay and jitter measurements are illustrated in Figure 5-14. Each MDP Agent (except for the first one on a path) can calculate the delay on its preceding network segment. Multiple delay types such as forwarding, processing, segment delays can be calculated as indicated by the formulas. Technically jitter can be calculated on any of the delay definitions, whereas the most important jitter metric is of course calculated on the cumulative E2E delay.

* Note: shows only the elements relevant in the MDP Agent's action's context

Figure 5-14 Timestamping and delay/jitter measurements.

The MDP Agents perform packet level loss detection, as shown in Figure 5-15, localized to the segments as illustrated in Figure 5-12. The packet loss is detected based on sequence numbers inserted into the data-plane encapsulation to make packet loss detection a capability that is independent of any higher layer protocol level sequence numbers (if at all present).

* Note: shows only the elements relevant in the MDP Agent's action's context

Figure 5-15 Packet loss detection.

The packet scheduling functionality of the MDP Agent is shown in Figure 5-16. In principle, the MDP Agent that needs to perform packet scheduling is the one fronting a network bottleneck. In wireless systems, this is often the radio interface, with the added complexity of the changing radio conditions and consequently the changing of the channel's capacity in terms of application layer throughput. The idea of the MDP Agent's scheduler is to measure the bottleneck's useful capacity and perform an upfront redistribution of this capacity among the competing flow mix (deterministic and non-deterministic). The redistribution considers the demand of each flow and can decrease the serving rate of non-deterministic traffic to enable the proper service of deterministic flows. However, the aim is to simply not overprovision (or strictly prioritize) deterministic traffic but to provide them with the right scheduling slots that maintain their required traffic characteristics and meets their declared QoS targets.

Figure 5-16 Packet scheduling.

The MDP Agent that performs scheduling must measure the capacity of the downstream bottleneck. Figure 5-17 illustrates an adaptive algorithm that enables to estimate the capacity by detecting symptoms of early delay build-up and eventually even losses (although in principle losses are to be avoided), which indicate that the bottleneck is being saturated with the current traffic mix. In this case, the measured throughput is a good estimate of the cumulative capacity of the underlying network interface. This capacity (actually, a slightly decreased amount, e.g., 95% of the estimated capacity) is then used as the cumulative service rate at the MDP Agent's own scheduler. This effectively pulls the bottleneck from the downstream point into the MDP Agent's scheduler and let's this scheduler enforce a different, deterministic flow aware service scheme over the traffic mix. The traffic forwarded from the MDP Agent's scheduler still meets the downstream network bottleneck, but being shaped below its momentary capacity, the network will not modulate the packet service significantly. That is, if the MDP Agent was able to ensure that flows with deterministic demand are served properly within its own scheduler, their service is not countered by the rest of the network's non-deterministic aware mechanisms. Of course, as the momentary capacity is dynamically changing, this estimation is continuously running in a capacity seeking manner, probing for more capacity when there is no delay build up, and decreasing whenever early signs of delay build-up is encountered. While this is an indirect mechanism, it has the benefit of not needing any support from the underlying network technology, and this is exactly the scenario that the MDP Agent technique is targeting.

Figure 5-17 Calibration of the scheduling rate by detecting and measuring the network's bottleneck capacity in real-time.

The MDP Agents may perform packet replication and elimination both to increase E2E reliability of the deterministic service and to always benefit from the lowest delay across the involved paths. Figure 5-18 illustrates the actions the MDP Agent to perform packet replication (shown for replicating a flow into two sub-flows, however replication into more sub-flows is also possible). The elimination counterpart is shown in Figure 5-19, again for two sub-flows.

* Note: shows only the elements relevant in the MDP Agent's action's context

Figure 5-18 Packet replication.

Figure 5-19 Packet elimination.

The data-plane encapsulation used by the MDP Agent contains the following information elements (also indicating the potential number of bytes for encoding, which however is not bounding and could be changed by an implementation):

- MDP Agent ID (4 bytes): an identity of the MDP Agent that is unique within the PREDICT-6G deployment. It is used to distinguish measurements reported by the various MDP Agents on segments (see Figure 5-12), including their direction (i.e., Segment A from MDP Agent 1 to MDP Agent 2 is different from Segment A from MDP Agent 2 to MDP Agent 1).
- E2E flow ID (4 bytes): an identity of the deterministic service flow that is unique within the PREDICT-6G deployment at a given time.
- Timestamp in nanosecond (8 bytes): used to timestamp the packets and serve as a basis of delay/jitter calculation.
- Accumulated delay in nanosecond (4 bytes): used to forward the measurement of the packet piggybacked on the packet itself to inform downstream MDP Agents about the delay already spent by this packet in forwarding.
- Sequence number, packet level (4 bytes): per flow sequence numbering to enable packet loss detection.
- Sub-flow number (2 bytes): used in coordination with packet replication and elimination. The first byte indicates the number of total sub-flows into which the flow is split (i.e., number of packet replica). The second byte indicates the instance number of the sub-flow to which the packet belongs to. For example, 0x00 on a packet means no split happened; 0x21 means two sub-flows exist and this is the 1st instance of the packet.

The data-plane encapsulation of the MDP Agent can be mapped to network protocol stack in multiple alternative ways. The alternatives are depicted in an end-to-end path that involves various baseline protocol stacks, such as Application (App) / UDP / IP at the end device or intermediate devices with no further encapsulation or having an additional GTP / UDP / IP tunnel that is the case in in 3GPP networks. These cover the most relevant paths on the example deployment depicted in Figure 5-10. The presented alternatives are listed with no preference in a particular implementation; they are provided to demonstrate different options for technical feasibility.

- **Alternative 1:** encapsulation similar to the IPsec transport mode (RFC4301, 2005) (Figure 5-20).
- **Alternative 2:** encapsulation similar to the IPsec tunnel mode (RFC4301, 2005) (Figure 5-21).
- **Alternative 3:** encapsulation using tunnel mode with UDP (Figure 5-22).
- **Alternative 4:** encapsulation using tunnel mode with UDP and additional GTP optimization to maximize MTU (Figure 5-23).

Figure 5-20 MDP data-plane encapsulation in transport mode.

In summary, the non-deterministic networks and devices may be handled through a dynamically deployed data-plane agent (MDP Agent) that provides complementary capabilities to the hosting network technology, adding the necessary mechanisms to support end-to-end deterministic flows. The concept is implemented in the Nokia Open Lab in a real test network with two technology domains: a non-deterministic 5G network and an IP transport network. The MDP Agent provides the PREDICT-6G MDP capabilities by implementing the MDP OpenAPIs, and it is integrated with the AICP components to enable automated deterministic service provisioning. The solution will be part of the deterministic services for critical communication use case demonstration. The integration of the PREDICT-6G components, including the MDP Agent, is ongoing according to (PREDICT-6G/D4.2, 2024) and will be ready in Q1 2025.

Figure 5-23 MDP data-plane encapsulation using tunnel mode with UDP and additional GTP optimization to maximize MTU.

5.6 Standardization aspects

During the lifetime of the project, WP2-related SDO contributions accounted for 33% of all contributions PREDICT-6G reported to the 6G-IA pre-standardization WG. Table 5-1 provides the updated data for the Period January 2023 – 30 November 2024, which can be also found on the SNS JU page (SNS-JU-SDO, 2024).

Table 5-1 WP2-Related SDO Contributions

Quarter	SDO	WG	Title
Q1 2023	IETF	DetNet	OAM for DetNet
	IETF	RAW	OAM features for RAW
	IETF	DetNet	Deterministic Networking (DetNet) Controller Plane Framework
	IETF	RAW	RAW multi-domain extensions
	IETF	RAW	MIPv6 RAW mobility
Q3 2023	IEEE	802.11 UHR	Scheduled channel access
Q3 2024	IETF	DetNet	Using Deterministic Networks for Industrial Operations and Control
Q4 2024	IETF	DetNet	Data Unit Groups for DetNet-Enabled Networks
	IETF	BM	Calibration of Measured Time Values between Network Elements

6 Open APIs

6.1 Summary of updates

The OpenAPIs between the PREDICT-6G MDP (data-plane) and AICP (control/management plane) were first introduced in Section 6 of (PREDICT-6G/D2.1, 2023) in general, followed by the analysis of those domain level AICP Management Services that do require interaction with the MDP in Section 11 of (PREDICT-6G/D1.2, 2023). In this deliverable, Section 6.2 to Section 6.5 provide a human readable summary for each API or set of APIs where the interaction between the MDP and a corresponding domain level AICP Management Service was anticipated. While the APIs could be consumed by any other MS (leaving implementation options open for flexible combination of MSs), the candidate requestor is noted for each API that is the likely/recommended consumer in the PREDICT-6G reference architecture. Following that, basic API operations are explained in a human readable manner but already mapping them to CRUD (create, read, update, delete) operations that fit the HTTP/REST API implementations. Finally, link to the PREDICT-6G GitLab repository is provided where the YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML) definition of the APIs are available.

6.2 Times sync

The Time Sync API follows the operation described in Section 8.2, 9.4, 11.3.1 of (PREDICT-6G/D1.2, 2023) with regards do 3GPP MDP-AICP integration.

Candidate requestor: SW implementation of Time Sync domain level AICP MS

- GET Domain Time Sync Capabilities
 - **Input:** None
 - **Output:** List of capabilities – is Grand Master (GM) capable
- POST Domain Time Sync Configuration
 - **Input:** Tim Synch Configuration (format depends on the MDP technology, e.g., 3GPP defined); PTP time domain ID; whether the domain shall act as GM
 - **Output:** Success/Failure as HTTP Code.
- GET/POST Time Sync status update: depends on the MDP way of operation – push or pull based (in 3GPP, push based)
- GET (to MDP)/POST (to domain Time Synch MS) Domain Time Sync status update (depending on the MDP technology, it may be either push or pull API; e.g., in 3GPP, it is push based))

- **Input:** ID of the configuration
- **Output:** Change in GM/follower roles

The YAML definition of the Time Sync API is available at:

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/Predict-6G-TimeSynch.yaml>

6.3 Deterministic service provisioning, decommissioning, updates

Candidate requestor: SW implementation of Resource Configuration or Service Automation domain level AICP MS

- POST Domain service
 - **Input:** Endpoint IDs, Service QoS specification, preferred path (if available)
 - **Output:**
 - (SUCCESS) ID from MDP related to the correspondent entity (e.g., flow)
 - (FAILURE) Failure message or HTTP Error code or both
- DELETE Domain service
 - **Input:** MDP ID
 - **Output:** Delete confirmation
- UPDATE Domain Service
 - Implemented by a pair of create (new service) / delete (old service) operations.
- GET Domain service
 - **Input:** MDP ID
 - **Output:** Status of the service

The YAML definition of the service API is available at (for multiple MDP technologies):

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/3gpp-configuration.yaml>

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/detnet-configuration.yaml>

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/tsn-configuration.yaml>

<https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/wifi-configuration.yaml>

6.4 Exposure of services: topology, capabilities, resources

Candidate requestor: SW implementation of any Exposure type domain level AICP MS

- GET Topology info (used to determinate the path of a service)
 - **Input:** None
 - **Output:** Network graph including
 - (DetNet) Nodes' resources
 - (DetNet) Node type (e.g., GW, which is important also for E2E Topology)
 - (DetNet) Link Capabilities
- GET Node/Link
 - **Input:** Node/Link ID
 - **Output:** Node/Link Info
- GET Network Capabilities
 - **Input:** None
 - **Output:** List of capabilities

The YAML definition of the exposure API (topology with resources and capabilities) is available at:

https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/topology_exposure_v2.0.yaml

6.5 Measurements and data collection

Candidate requestor: SW implementation of the Measurement Collection domain level AICP MS

- GET KPI info
 - **Input:** none

- **Output:** KPIs
 - Reliability
 - Availability
 - Packet loss
 - Packet ordering
 - Latency
 - Jitter
 - Throughput

The YAML definition of the Measurement Collection API is available at:

https://gitlab.netcom.it.uc3m.es/predict-6g/openapis/mdp-openapis/-/blob/main/data_collection/PREDICT-6G_Data_Collection.yaml

7 Roadmap

In Table 7-1 we include the agreed roadmap of the integration of Work Package 2 until the end of the project.

Table 7-1 Roadmap of WP2 integration until the end of the project

Technology specific MS in AICP	Nokia lab	5Tonic				
		Ericsson 3GPP - DetNet	TID TSN	UC3M TSN - DetNet	UC3M WIFI - DetNet	IDE-DetNet (DUG)
Time sync	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
Measurement collection	Yes	Yes All done but API ASAP	Yes Q1-2025	Yes Q1-2025	Yes Q1-2025	Yes Q42024
Resource Config. /SA	Yes	Yes ASAP	Yes Q1-2025	Yes Q4-2024	Yes Q4-2024	Yes Q1-2025
Topology exposure	Yes	Yes Q4-2024	TBD	Yes Q1-2025	Yes Q1-2025	Yes Q4-2024
Capability exposure	Yes					Yes
Resource exposure	Yes	N/A		Yes Q1-2025	Yes Q1-2025	N/A

8 Conclusions

This deliverable provided an update to the results and technical advances created for the multi-domain data plan of PREDICT-6G since the first release of MDP. The key areas with novel results include resource allocation and scheduling mechanisms, using the rTWT mechanism of Wi-Fi 802.11be for TSN emulation, and seamless Wi-Fi 7 roaming with multi-link operation. The deliverable reported on the detailed design of a distributed mechanism to emulate deterministic features in non-deterministic networks. Additionally, the deliverable provides the experience from a successful cross-domain integration of TSN, Wi-Fi and 3GPP using DetNet in a real testbed using commercial equipment. OpenAPIs to all MDP capabilities are now defined in YAML, available in PREDICT-6G's GitLab. The deliverable concludes by providing the roadmap to implement and demonstrate the novel features during the rest of the project timeline.

9 Publications

Following, we summarize the publications where WP2 has a significant contribution:

- (Cabrera-Bean, Pan and Vidal, 2024) M. Cabrera-Bean, W. Pan, J. Vidal (2024) “Reinforcement Learning-based UL/DL Splitter for Latency Reduction in Wireless TSN Networks”, 2024 IEEE 100th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2024-Fall), Washington DC, October 2024.
- (El Kaisi, Villares and Muñoz, 2024) Y. El Kaisi, J. Villares, O. Muñoz, “Novel Radio Frame Design for Efficient Integration of Wireless Links into Time-Sensitive Networks” IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC), Valencia (Spain), September 2024.
- (Mollà and Lorenzo, 2024) M Mollà, M Lorenzo, “Smart De-jittering using Network Digital Twin”, IEEE International Mediterranean Conference on Communications and Networking (MeditCom), June 2024
- (Robitzsch et al., 2024) S. Robitzsch, C. Sarathchandra, M. Starsinic and X. De Foy, "Formation and Assertion of Data Unit Groups in 3GPP Networks with TSN and PDU Set Support," 2024 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 2024, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/WCNC57260.2024.10570842
- (Robitzsch et al., Globecom, 2024) Robitzsch, S., de la Oliva, A., Chiasserini, C. F., Casetti, C. E., Agraz, F., Landi, G., Contreras Murillo, L. M., Szilagyi, P., Giardina, P. G., Rosales, R., Spadaro, S., & Frascolla, V. (2024, October 4). Standardisation Assessment of a Digital Twin-Based Multi-Domain Deterministic Communications System. IEEE Global Communications Conference 2024 (2024 IEEE Globecom), Cape Town, South Africa. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13891449>
- (Rico-Menéndez et al., 2024) Experimentation in a wireless multi-domain deterministic networks: the SLICES-Madrid

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